

Southern California CSU DNP Consortium

California State University, Fullerton
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EVALUATING PERCEPTIONS OF SUBSTANCE USE DISORDER
AMONG EMERGENCY NURSES

A DOCTORAL PROJECT

Submitted in Partial Fulfillment of the Requirements

For the degree of

DOCTOR OF NURSING PRACTICE

By

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ABSTRACT

Substance use disorder (SUD), a condition that occurs when recurrent alcohol and/or drug use causes clinically significant impairment, is estimated to affect at least 10% of Registered Nurses (RNs), especially in the critical care setting. Impaired nurses present serious risks to patient safety, the physical and psychological wellbeing of the impaired nurse, and the integrity of the nursing profession. Early identification and intervention of SUD in nursing is essential for safe patient care and nursing integrity. Nursing colleagues can be the first to identify an impaired coworker. An anonymous, five-item survey evaluating RN perceptions of SUD among bed-side nurses was administered in a 24-bed Emergency Department (ED). Twenty-seven RNs (65.9%) responded; the majority were females who worked full-time, and half of the respondents had five years or less experience working in the ED. Full-time RNs were not as capable of identifying risk factors of SUD as part-time and per diem nurses. While respondents often identified that reporting a colleague could lead to mandatory entry into a treatment program, perceptions varied as to what happens to an RN colleague once they are reported for suspected on-the-job impairment. These findings support the development of a mandatory online education module to address the misconceptions surrounding SUD as well as clarify the hospital-specific recommendations for addressing nursing SUD.

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BACKGROUND

Substance use disorder (SUD) is defined as a pattern of behavioral symptoms that occurs when recurrent alcohol and/or drug use causes clinically significant impairment (Substance and Mental Health Services Administration [SAMHSA], 2019). Due to the stigma and secrecy behind substance use, accurate data concerning substance-related impairment of nurses in the workplace has been inconsistent (Bozimowski et al., 2014; Emergency Nurses Association [ENA], 2016; NCSBN, 2011). Cares, Pace, Denious and Cran (2015) reported 47.6% (n = 120) of licensed and registered nurses enrolled in a treatment program for substance use disorder (SUD) reported using drugs or alcohol while at work, posing significant risk to patient safety. In an anonymous electronic survey, Kunyk (2015) found that 97.5% of nurses (n = 289) with SUD were not known to their employers. Substance use disorder among nurses poses considerable risks to patient safety, the nurse's health and welfare, and the nursing profession.

Problem Statement

In 2011, the National Council of State Boards of Nursing (NCSBN) reported that one in ten nurses suffers from drug or alcohol dependency. Substance use disorder affects approximately 10% of American nurses, or roughly 340,000 individuals (Kaiser Family Foundation, 2018; NCSBN, 2016). Hospital-based nurses working in critical care areas such as the Emergency Department (ED) and the Intensive Care Unit (ICU) are at an increased risk of SUD because of high levels of stress, increased burnout, and ease of access to controlled substances (Bozimowski, Groh, Rouen, & Dosch, 2014; Trinkoff & Storr, 1998).

Purpose Statement

The purpose of this project is to survey the perceptions of SUD among RNs in a local community hospital ED. The results of the survey will be analyzed and used to create an educational module to identify and address misconceptions related to the identification and reporting of SUD among RNs in the ED. The goal of this project is to increase the Emergency RNs' awareness of the prevalence and risk factors of SUD, as well as signs of coworker impairment and consequences of reporting an impaired colleague. It is hypothesized that the RNs will not be able to correctly identify what will happen to a colleague if they are reported for possible SUD. This may further decrease reporting and place patients and coworkers at risk. Ultimately, this survey and educational module may help to create an environment where RNs can correctly identify the prevalence and risk factors of SUD, the signs of coworker impairment, and correctly identify the hospital-specific process for the reporting and investigation of SUD.

Supporting Framework

Theoretical frameworks help detail, define, and predict the major aspects of a proposed phenomenon (Abend, 2008). In 1947, Kurt Lewin published his Change Theory, commonly called Unfreeze-Change-Refreeze, focusing on three major stages of implementing organizational change. Lewin described the opposing forces that affect the balance and capacity to enact lasting change in a dynamic environment (Lewin, 1947). Driving forces are those forces that propel the change, such as patient safety issues, recent policy changes, or public controversy (Kritsonis, 2005). Resisting forces are forces that repel the change; they are forces to be overcome when evaluating the need and capacity to change. Lewin defined change as three distinct processes with unique stages:

unfreezing, changing, and refreezing (Cummings, Bridgman, & Brown, 2016). When trying to enact lasting change, it is essential to evaluate the unique needs and concepts of each of these phases.

Unfreeze

The first phase of Lewin's Change Theory is *unfreezing*. This phase involves uncovering the core beliefs, values, and behaviors inherent to the organization, the status quo (Lewin, 1947). Part of the unfreezing phase involves preparing the organization for the impending change through highlighting the core values and perceptions that may be inaccurate or outdated. Another aspect of *unfreezing* is evaluating the need for change and recruiting stakeholders who are invested in the impending change (Coming, Bridgman, & Brown, 2016). Ultimately, *unfreezing* involves creating motivation to change, identifying driving and resisting forces, and recruiting powerful stakeholders to empower the inevitable change.

For this doctoral project, local statistics on SUD and a review of literature will inform the need for a change in the perceptions, values, and behaviors of the RNs within the ED. Stakeholders such as the ED Director, Human Resources Director, Risk Management Director, the Chief Executive Officer (CEO), and the Chief Nursing Officer (CNO) will be presented with the local and national data concerning SUD, and recruited as powerful stakeholders for change. As part of the unfreezing phase, review of hospital-specific policies and procedures, as well as the California BRN disciplinary and Alternative to Discipline (ATD) program recommendations will be conducted to assess for driving or resisting forces for change. If the hospital policies and procedures are not supported by the California BRN recommendations, then amending those policies and

procedures will become part of the change plan. Finally, a five-item survey will be administered to the bedside RNs in the ED to uncover perceptions regarding SUD in the ED (see Figure 1).

Change

The second phase of Lewin's Change Theory is called the *change* phase. It focuses on moving the status quo in a new direction through purposeful, planned action (Lewin, 1947). Through developing and implementing a plan to change the values, perceptions, beliefs, or behaviors of a given organization, the *change* phase is action-based. This phase is arguably the hardest because of the difficulty of motivating change in others, especially when it is contrary to the organization's status quo. In this phase, it is essential to persuade employees that the status quo is no longer helpful to the organization (Kristonis, 2005). To help facilitate change, it is beneficial to enlist the support of leaders who are invested in the need for the change. The end goal of the *change* phase is to move the organization to a new level of equilibrium, a new status quo (Kritsonis, 2005).

Following the administration and analysis of the surveys, the results will be presented to the CNO and ED Director to not only disseminate findings, but also mobilize stakeholder commitment and support in the change. The survey data will be analyzed, reviewed, and compared to the evidence surrounding SUD uncovered in the review of literature. Finally, with the help of the hospital Education Department, an educational module will be created to address misconceptions and misinformation surrounding SUD among the nursing staff. This module will be presented to and

approved by the ED manager, further empowering the change project, and then subsequently presented to the Emergency RNs.

Refreeze

The final phase of Lewin's theory is called *refreezing*. *Refreezing* is an essential final step because change is typically short-lived, and people typically slide back into old behaviors and thinking. In *refreezing*, the new values should be integrated into the existing values and traditions of the organization (Kritsonis, 2005). To integrate change into a healthcare organization, policies and procedures should be created that formalize the change. The goal of the *refreezing* phase is to make the change "stick" and establish a new status quo. *Refreezing* is about internalizing and institutionalizing the change. Evaluation of the efficacy of the change project is a necessary component to ensure that the intended changes in values, beliefs, and behavior have occurred (Lewin, 1947). Reinforcing the change through formal mechanisms such as new orientation education or policies and procedures can be an effective strategy to integrating the new values within the organization. Future evaluation and assessment of the core values, perceptions, and behaviors within the organization is necessary to ensure the change has truly become the new status quo.

To ensure the institutionalization of the new perceptions, beliefs, and values presented in the educational module, the module will be adopted as a part of the yearly unit-specific nursing skills day. It will also be integrated as a mandatory orientation module for new and on-boarding RNs in the ED. Upon completion of the module a five-item post-test will be administered to assess the impact of the educational module. The

post-test will also be used to amend and revise the educational module to address discrepancies and improve the module accordingly.

Figure 1. Adaptation of Lewin's Change Theory by Bayhan.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

Overview

Nursing SUD is a dangerous problem that presents serious risks to patient safety, the physical and psychological wellbeing of the nurse with SUD, and the integrity of the nursing profession (Strobbe & Crowley, 2017; NSCBN). SUD is estimated to affect at least 10% of nurses, especially in the critical care setting (Trinkoff & Storre, 1998; Strobbe & Crowley, 2017). Impaired RNs pose considerable risks to patient safety as well as their own health and wellbeing (Weenink et al., 2017). Early identification and intervention of SUD in nursing is of utmost importance, especially with the increase of opioid prescribing and five-fold increase in overdose deaths in the U.S. (CDC, 2017).

Literature Review

A comprehensive search of the literature using PubMed, CINAHL, PsycINFO was conducted for articles published between January 2013 and April 30, 2018 (see Table of Evidence in Appendix A). Additional website searches were conducted using Google Scholar, the Emergency Nurses Association, the International Nurses Society on Addiction, and the American Nurses Association for relevant content. A search for select gray literature (i.e., unpublished research, dissertations, and editorials) and an examination of the references of key articles, as well as direct contact with authors for supplemental data was also completed. Key search topics included substance use in nurses, risk factors for substance use in nursing, barriers to reporting and seeking treatment, and facilitators to limit substance abuse and increase reporting. Searches were limited to peer-reviewed journal articles published in the English language, as well as

seminal publications outside of the inclusion date range. A university librarian was consulted and search terms were modified according to recommendations.

Additional subheading search terms and themes included: Emergency Department, acute care, critical care, risk factors, statistics, incidence, prevalence, barriers, and facilitators in substance abuse awareness and reporting among nurses. Publications were excluded if they focused on nursing management of patients with SUD or substance use among nurses outside of the acute care setting, with the exception of student nurses. While *substance use disorder* is the preferred terminology used in the Joint Position Statement by the ENA and IntNSA, for the purposes of this literature search, *substance abuse* and *substance use* were used because the majority of literature on *substance use disorder* focused on patient diagnosis, perceptions, and management.

The literature review followed a systematic approach. Table 1 is an illustration of the search results, including database and specific search terms. Exact numbers of articles retrieved for each keyword search is listed, and all article titles and abstracts were reviewed for inclusion for this literature review. Articles were excluded based on subject relevance, clinical setting, and duplication. Articles that included non-related commentary, abstracts, and focused exclusively on smoking were omitted from the literature review. Thirty-two articles were used for the final literature review.

Table 1

PubMed, CINAHL, and PsychINFO Database Searches

Topics	Search Terms	Articles Retrieved	PubMed	CINAHL	PsychINFO	Articles Used
Substance Abuse in Nursing	- substance use in nurses AND emergency room	260				9
	- substance use in nurses AND emergency department		7	0	0	
	- substance abuse in nurses AND emergency department		7	0	0	
	- substance abuse in nurses AND emergency room		41	0	0	
	- substance abuse in nurses AND acute care		30	0	2	
	- substance abuse in nurses AND critical care		16	0	1	
	- substance use in nurses AND emergency		29	2	1	
	- substance abuse in nurses AND statistics		12	2	1	
Risk Factors for Substance Abuse in Nursing	- substance use in nurses AND emergency	356	106	2	1	13
	- substance abuse in nurses AND risk factors		89	32	30	
	- substance abuse AND nurses AND access		65	27	25	
Barriers to Reporting and/or Seeking Treatment	- substance abuse AND nurses AND stress	71	37	24	27	5
	- substance use AND nurses AND barriers		15	24	21	
	- substance use AND nurses AND reporting AND barriers		1	0	1	
	- substance use AND nurses AND barriers AND seeking treatment		5	2	2	
Early Detection and Intervention	- substance use AND nurses AND barriers AND seeking help	56	0	0	0	6
	- substance use AND nurses AND facilitators		4	0	0	
	- substance use AND nurses AND reporting		9	15	1	
	- substance use AND nurses AND self-report		12	9	6	

Note. Articles were excluded based on title and relevance to project.

Substance Abuse in Nursing

The phrase *substance use disorder* has recently been adopted as the preferred phrase to describe the phenomenon of progressive, chronic craving and substance use to the point that it impairs one's ability to function safely (Davis et al., 2014; Kunyk, 2015; Monroe et al., 2013; Strobbe & Crowley, 2017). Other terms used in the recent literature include *substance misuse* (Bozimowski et al., 2014), *substance abuse* (Cares et al., 2015; Trinkoff & Storr, 1998), and *problematic substance use* (Ross et al., 2017). In reviewing the literature, search terms were adapted because *substance use disorder* appeared mainly as a patient diagnosis in the recent literature. Consequently, *substance use* and *substance abuse* were also used as search terms, yielding more appropriate nursing-focused results.

A ten percent prevalence of SUD among nurses (approximately 340,000 RNs) is estimated for this project because it mirrors the SUD prevalence in the general U.S. population (Kunyk, 2015; Monroe et al.; Strobbe & Crowley, 2017; Trinkoff & Storr, 1998). Some studies estimated a range of six to 20% prevalence of SUD among nurses (Ivey, 2015; Ross et al., 2017). Because of the team-based approach of most healthcare facilities, SUD among RNs can impact not only the individual nurse, but the team as well. Although SUD is widely accepted as a chronic, progressive disease process, it carries a social stigma with personal and professional ramifications (Cares et al., 2015; Kunyk).

Risk Factors

Nurses have an increased risk of SUD based upon their work environments, with the highest risk areas being oncology, psychiatric nursing, ED, and ICU (Trinkoff & Storr, 1998). Other major risk factors of SUD among RNs include work overload, stress,

and poor coping (Lala et al., 2016; Strobbe & Crowley, 2017). Other related risk factors include family history, depression, an in depth understanding of medications and mechanisms of action, and chronic pain (Cares et al., 2015; Darbro & Malliarkis, 2013; Pilgrim et al., 2017; Ross et al., 2017; Strobbe & Crowley, 2017). Knowledge of medications was also found as a risk factor for SUD among RNs (Pilgrim et al., 2017). Knowledge of medications may be linked with increased self-medicating and feelings of invulnerability (Pilgrim et al., 2017). Conversely, Bozimowski et al. (2014) found no identified risk factors for SUD in 50 percent of Student Registered Nurse Anesthetists (SRNAs), whose work environment has easy access to medications, while attending school. The culture of hospital nursing may perpetuate increased work stress and chronic pain as a reality of the nursing profession (Ross et al., 2017).

Risk factors of SUD include a family history of drug or alcohol dependence, mental illness, and chronic pain (Monroe et al.; Ross et al., 2017). Research indicates that within nursing, males and females are both at risk of SUD, but females tend to progress quicker into drug and alcohol dependence and make up the majority of drug-related deaths (Pilgrim et al., 2017; Worley, 2017). Other risk factors, in summary, include high personal or professional stress, high workload, access to controlled substances, and medication knowledge (Darbro & Driscoll, 2013; Konyk, 2015; Lala et al., 2016; Ross et al., 2017). The culture of the nursing profession may normalize long work hours, chronic stress, and risk of physical injury among nurses (Ross et al., 2017). Factors that may discourage self-reporting and reporting of colleagues include workplace culture and facility-related policies and procedures for addressing suspected SUD (Cares et al., 2015; Strobbe & Crowley, 2017; Ross et al., 2017).

Kunyk (2015) found that 49.8% of sampled RNs with SUD (n = 198) tested positive for mental illness according to the SF-12v12 Health Survey, a valid and reliable mental health screening tool. In a review of a national coroner database in Australia, Pilgrim et al. (2017) found that RNs had the highest rates of drug-caused deaths (69%) with other major risk factors being middle-aged, female, a history of mental illness, high stress, and self-harm intention.

While drug access was reported as a risk factor for SUD in most studies, one study proposed that access as a risk factor may be unfounded (Darbro & Malliarakis; Pilgrim et al., 2017; Strobbe & Crowley, 2017; Ross et al., 2017). Ross et al. (2017) postulate that access may be erroneously linked as causative when RN theft may be the more accurate risk factor. Opioids are the most frequently abused controlled substances, followed by benzodiazepines (Bozimowski et al., 2014; Pilgrim et al., 2017). Concomitant alcohol and controlled substance use increases the odds by 5.9 times of RN recidivism, new violations after completing SUD-related treatment, and probation (Davis et al., 2014). Davis et al. (2014) examined the risk of recidivism, concluding that males were at 23.7% increased risk of recidivism (n = 36). The researchers found that length of probation had no statistically significant impact on recidivism, meaning longer probationary periods did not impact RN recidivism (Davis et al., 2014).

Barriers to Reporting and Seeking Treatment

Social stigma, lack of knowledge on the prevalence and signs of SUD, and fear of losing one's nursing license are the main barriers to reporting SUD in the acute care setting (Cares et al., 2015; Ross et al., 2017). SUD is often viewed as a weakness of character, a lack of morals, and a lack of willpower (Darbro, 2015; Kunyk et al., 2011;

Ross et al., 2017). Punitive policies and lack of RN knowledge of the consequences of reporting perpetuate a culture of silence and may limit self-reporting and reporting from colleagues (Ross et al., 2017; Worley, 2017). Possible barriers to seeking treatment include embarrassment, feelings of hopelessness, lack of employer support, and fear of losing one's RN license (Cares et al., 2015; Kunyk, 2015). Nurses do not feel confident in their ability to identify impaired colleagues and lack overall education about SUD prevalence and signs among RNs (Cares et al., 2015; Darbro & Malliarakis, 2015; Kunyk, 2015).

Early Detection and Intervention

Early detection and intervention are recommended to facilitate treatment of SUD among RNs (Cares et al., 2015; Worley, 2017). Some studies found that nurses should be screened in nursing school, and that nursing schools should adopt an ATD program instead of a disciplinary approach to SUD (Bozimowski et al., 2014; Ross et al., 2017). Each state Board of Nursing (BON) creates its own rules and regulations regarding SUD and disciplinary action. Most states have either a disciplinary approach, where the RN may face public exposure, loss of license, and criminal charges, or an ATD program, where the RN is placed into a treatment program, loses his/her license for a probationary period, and then reenters nursing upon successful completion of the program. Despite recommendations and the high success of ATD programs, only 73% of BONs have ATD programs in place (Monroe et al., 2013). ATD programs have a 90 - 95% success rate and empower RNs to safely return to nursing practice (Weenink et al., 2017; Wright et al., 2014). The ATD program should be administered independently of the hospital and governing boards (Worley, 2017). While most BONs have an ATD program in place,

there is no standardization of SUD treatment between states (Worley, 2017).

Standardized treatment of SUD should be established among the nursing profession with education about SUD encouraged as mandatory continuing education (Zickafoose, 2018).

Nurse managers and coworkers can be the first to identify SUD but lack the knowledge and tools to effectively evaluate high-risk behaviors that may be indicators of the disorder (Cadiz et al., 2015; Darbro & Driscoll, 2013; Kunyk, 2015). Through supportive ATD policies, transparency, and ongoing education, management can create and maintain an environment that values safety, trust, and encourages increased reporting of SUD (Cares et al., 2015; Darbro & Driscoll, 2013; Kunyk, 2015; Zickafoose, 2018).

Most RNs believe that rehabilitation from SUD is possible and that individual confidentiality should be maintained (Kunyk, 2015). Early identification and intervention are essential to promote patient safety and empower RNs with SUD to attain lasting recovery (Kunyk, 2015; Monroe et al., 2013). Recovery programs (i.e., 12-step programs) and trigger management are personal strategies for managing SUD among RNs to sustain recovery (Wright et al., 2014). Random urine drug screening can be a barrier to relapse and drug use in the workplace (Darbro & Driscoll, 2013; Pilgrim et al., 2017; Wright et al., 2014), and an independently regulated ATD program is recommended for RNs identified with SUD (Weenink et al., 2017; Wright et al., 2014).

External support factors include hospital policies upholding ATD programs and ongoing mandatory RN education on SUD (Wright, 2014; Zickafoose, 2018).

Bozimowski et al. (2014) support random drug screening for student nurses, as well as ATD programs, instead of disciplinary programs, for nursing schools. Random urine drug screening was found to be a deterrent among RNs in the hospital setting, as well as

student RNs with SUD (Bozimowski et al., 2014; Wright et al., 2014). Early prevention, treatment, and education improved adherence outcomes for sustained SUD recovery (Cares et al., 2015; Weenink et al., 2017).

METHODS

This project used a survey to identify four major perceptions of SUD among a specific group of Emergency RNs (see survey in Appendix B). The four perceptions are: (a) prevalence of SUD among Emergency RNs, (b) risk factors of SUD for RNs, (c) signs of coworker impairment, and (d) consequences of reporting suspected SUD. These four perception categories are based on findings from the literature. A five-item survey was developed from a review of the literature as well as adapted survey items obtained from a previous study conducted by Cares et al. (2015). To create the survey items, Cares et al. used subject matter experts, focus group reviews, and psychometric testing. The survey questions were used with permission from Peer Assistance Service, Inc., Denver Colorado (see Appendix C).

The first survey item was created to assess the underlying perception of the prevalence of SUD. Research shows that many nurses underestimate the prevalence of SUD among nurses (Kunyk, 2015; Monroe et al., 2013). Referencing the statistics published by the ENA and ANA, the survey item incorporates recent statistics on the number of nurses in the U.S. as well as estimated percentages. This item will serve as a baseline launching point for the subsequent educational module. The additional answer option of “Other, please describe” will enable staff to write in their own perceptions of the prevalence of SUD, help guide educational needs, and further assess underlying perceptions.

The second survey item was developed to evaluate the underlying perceptions of the staff about the major risk factors of SUD. The review of literature revealed several themes as major risk factors: work overload, stress, and poor coping (Darbro & Driscoll,

2013; Kunyk, 2015; Lala et al., 2016; Ross et al., 2017), depression, access to medications, understanding of medications and chronic pain (Cares et al., 2015; Darbro & Malliarkis; Pilgrim et al., 2017; Ross et al., 2017; Strobbe & Crowley, 2017). Once again, “Other, please describe” as an answer option will facilitate a deeper exploration and understanding of the baseline major perceptions of risk factors.

The third survey item was created to assess the baseline perceptions of the nursing staff’s self-believed ability to identify and impaired coworker. Cares et al. (2015) found that 37% of participants (n = 112) felt that their SUD could have been discovered earlier by a nursing coworker or employer. This survey item is explored more comprehensively in the subsequent fourth item.

Survey item four further outlines observable behaviors associated with SUD among coworkers. Cadiz et al. (2017), Cares et al. (2015) and Kunyk (2015) found that RNs do not feel capable to adequately identify an impaired colleague and require further education of observable behaviors of an impaired colleague. This survey item was adapted from a checklist created by Cadiz et al. to help management identify and intervene when suspecting an impaired nurse. The Cadiz et al. tool was developed after a through literature review and focus group refinement. The authors found five thematic behavior subsets: Attendance/Work Pattern Changes; Cognitive Performance; Interpersonal/Social Performance; Physical Performance; and Policy Adherence/Drug Diversion. As with prior survey items, “Other, please describe” was included to elicit individualized responses that were not anticipated and give the participants freedom to express their perceptions.

The final survey item was adapted from survey item # 15 in the Cares et al. survey. This survey item was designed to elicit perceived consequences of reporting. Cares et al. (2015) and Kunyk (2015) identified these main concepts as possible barriers to reporting. This item will guide the future creation of the educational module by assessing the underlying perceptions of the consequences of reporting. Correcting these misconceptions may improve future reporting of impaired colleagues.

A content expert was consulted for review of the adapted five-item survey to be used for this project. The content expert has extensive experience in mental health nursing and SUD and has worked as a consultant for the California Board of Registered Nurses to create evidence-based continuing education modules on SUD. She reviewed and approved the content and wording used in the survey-items to ensure accuracy as well as minimize bias. The survey to be used for this project is described in Appendix B.

Approval was obtained from the ED Director, the Director of Human Resources, the Director of Risk Management, and the Chief Nursing Officer (CNO). To maintain anonymity, only basic demographic information was obtained and a cover letter consent was used (see Appendix D). The original surveys were kept in a locked drawer in the office of the Director of Emergency Services.

With the assistance of the hospital Director of Education, an educational module will be created to present findings of the survey as well as educate the Emergency RNs on knowledge gaps identified in the original survey. The proposed module will be presented to the ED manager and the Department of Education for final approval before being presented to Emergency RNs. Immediately following completion of the module, a

post-test survey will be administered to test subsequent knowledge and perceptions of SUD among Emergency RNs.

Setting

This survey on the perceptions of SUD took place in a 24-bed Emergency Department within a 114-bed acute-care facility on the West Coast of the United States. This ED provides comprehensive, 24-hour emergency medical services that employ RNs for variable 12-hour shifts:

- Day shift: 7 A.M. - 7:30 P.M.
- Cross shifts: 9 A.M. - 9:30 P.M., 11 A.M. - 11:30 P.M., 1 P.M. - 1:30 A.M., and 3 P.M. – 3:30 A.M.
- Night shift: 7 P.M. - 7:30 A.M.

The nurse-to-patient ratio is 1:4 unless the patient is identified as more critical (i.e., triaged with an Emergency Severity Index [ESI] of 1 or 2 (see Appendix E), at which point the ratio becomes 1:2 or 1:1, depending on necessary resources. To manage Emergency RN workload and minimize stress, management tries to maintain a 1:3 nurse-to-patient ratio, but those ratios tend to be 1:4 on night shift. Because the highest patient census occurs between 9 A.M. and 1 A.M., the cross shifts are typically the busiest shifts with the greatest patient census.

Within the ED there are 17 full-time (FT) RNs, 11 part-time (PT) RNs, and 13 per diem (PD) RNs (total staff of 41 RNs). Shift hours are tightly monitored and regulated by ED managers, and RNs are not allowed to exceed 12 hours of work per 24-hour period, with a total not to exceed 40 hours per week. Resources are minimal on night shifts (i.e.,

7 - 7:30 P.M.) with no director or manager, and minimal staffing, typically one ED doctor, one unit secretary, and four to six nurses.

Sample

Inclusion criteria for this sample will include all RNs who work as bedside nurses in the ED. Basic demographic information will be obtained, including gender (male, female, or other), employment status (full-time [FT], part-time [PT], or per diem [PD]), and years employed (given in five-year ranges). Exclusion criteria for this project will include non-nursing ED staff, ED management, and student RNs.

Ethical Concerns

Verbal approval for the use of the survey from the CNO, HR, Risk Management, and the ED Director was obtained on February 12, 2018. Institutional Review Board (IRB) approval was sought from the hospital, and the project was deemed to be exempt from IRB approval, pending IRB approval from the educational institute. Written permission to implement the project was obtained from the CNO to ensure transparency and ongoing approval across all levels within the hospital (see Appendix D).

An IRB application was submitted to the California State University, Fullerton Review Board. Supplementary documentation for survey administration included the survey cover letter consent (see Appendix F) and the Employee Assistance Program resources (see Appendix G). The project was deemed a quality improvement project and therefore exempt from IRB with special consideration for maintaining ethical considerations (see Appendix H). Upon CSUF IRB approval, surveys were distributed and data collection began.

Plan for Data Collection

At the suggestion of the CNO, paper and pencil surveys were posted at two main RN gatherings within the ED: the nurse huddle board and the ED break room. A durable lockbox with a slit opening was installed at the huddle board with instructions for anonymous submission of surveys into the lockbox. This lockbox key was kept by the primary investigator and the box was checked thrice weekly by the primary investigator. The survey was discussed and promoted at 7:20AM and 7:20PM by the ED Care Coordinators, the nurse managers within the unit. Surveys were subsequently kept in the locked drawer of the ED Director's office until transported in total to the locked home office drawer of the lead investigator. Completed surveys were collected for two weeks, from October 29 to November 9, 2018.

The surveys collected brief demographic information including gender, employment status, shift worked, and years in the ED (see Appendix B). The survey items collected categorical responses that were used for data analysis. Most survey items also had an option to select "Other: Please explain" to gather subjective data as well as empower the participants to express their perceptions without limits.

RESULTS

The anonymous surveys were collected for analysis with careful consideration both for quantitative and qualitative data. While the survey allowed respondents to free-write perceptions throughout the brief survey, only eight respondents provided qualitative input. For data analysis, a statistician was consulted and the resulting data analysis and discussion was reviewed with a PhD-prepared nurse researcher. The resulting data analysis will then be used to create an educational module to be presented to ED management and RN staff.

After two weeks, survey collection was closed with a total of 27 surveys anonymously collected for a response rate of 65.9%. Statistical analysis was performed using Intellectus™ software. Descriptive analysis was performed on the demographic information provided by the respondents with frequencies and percentages displayed in Table 2. These descriptive variables were analyzed for frequencies and trends.

The majority of respondents were female (n = 20, 74%) and were employed as a full-time RN (n = 20, 74%). Employment status was fairly evenly distributed among respondents with the majority working AM (n = 10, 37%) or PM shifts (n = 10, 37%). 66.7% of the respondents had worked as an RN for ten years or less. The largest group of respondents within the “Years Worked” demographic had worked five years or less (n = 13, 48.2%). Roughly half of the participants have 0 – 5 years of nursing experience (n = 13). Table 3 illustrates that 48.15% of the 27 respondents have five years or less of experience in the ED.

Table 2

Frequency Table for Demographic Attributes

Variable	<i>n</i>	%
Gender		
Female	20	74.07
Male	7	25.93
Employment Status		
Full -Time	20	74.07
Part -Time	2	7.41
Per Diem	5	18.52
Shift Worked		
PM	10	37.04
AM	10	37.04
Cross/Split Shift	6	22.22
Missing	1	3.70
Years Worked		
0 – 5 Years	13	48.15
6 – 10 Years	5	18.52
11 – 15 Years	3	11.11
16 – 20 Years	4	14.81
21 or More Years	2	7.41

Note. Due to rounding errors, percentages may not equal 100%.

Table 3

Frequency Table for Years Worked

Variable	<i>n</i>	%
Years Worked		
0 – 5 Years	13	48.15
6 Years or More	14	51.85

Note. Due to rounding errors, percentages may not equal 100%.

Survey item responses were also analyzed with distribution and percentages displayed in Table 4. For the first question asking about the participant's perception of the prevalence of SUD among RNs, more participants selected 15% or 20% ($n = 13$, 48.15%), while six participants (22.22%) selected 2% or 5%. Eight participants (29.63%) correctly identified a 10% prevalence rate. Two participants chose not to select any of the discreet options. In the dedicated area for comments, one participant wrote in "40%" and the other wrote in "None."

Table 4

Frequency Table for Distribution of Responses

Variable	<i>n</i>	%
Question 1 – Incidence of SUD		
< 10%	6	22.22
10%	6	22.22
> 10%	13	48.15
Missing	2	7.14
Question 2 – Identify Major Risk Factors		
0 – 3 Risk Factors Identified	12	44.44
4 - 7 Risk Factors Identified	8	29.63
All 8 Risk Factors Identified	7	25.93
Question 3 – Can Identify Impaired Coworker		
Yes	19	70.37
No	5	18.52
Unsure	3	11.11
Question 4 – Identify Observable Behaviors		
< 4 Behaviors	13	48.15
> 4 Behaviors	13	48.15
Missing	1	3.70

Note. Due to rounding errors, percentages may not equal 100%.

For Question 2, identifying risk factors, the most frequently selected answers were “stress” and “access to medication” (n = 25, 92.59% respectively). The least common response was “financial commitments” (n = 8, 29.63%). For the purpose of further statistical analysis, the respondents were grouped into comparable groups: those who identified less than four risk factors (n = 12, 44.44%) and those who identified four or more risk factors (n = 15, 55.56%). In total, seven (25.93%) participants correctly identified all eight risk factors. One participant wrote in “Work management/Politics” as an additional risk factor for SUD among RNs.

The third survey item focused on whether or not the participant believed he/she could correctly identify an impaired coworker. Nineteen participants (70.37%) self-identified as being able to identify an impaired coworker. Five participants (18.52%) selected that they could not, and three (11.11%) were unsure whether they could identify an impaired coworker.

Question 4 evaluated the participants’ ability to identify observable behaviors associated with an impaired coworker. The most commonly selected item was “takes extended breaks during the shift, sometimes without telling coworkers” (n = 25, 92.59%). The next most commonly selected item was “reports medication being wasted when it was not” (n = 23, 85.19%). “Changes in speech” was the least selected item, with only 18 participants (66.67%) selecting it as an observable behavior of an impaired coworker. For this survey item, many participants wrote in comments in the section for dedicated free text. These responses included:

- Puncture site markings
- Offers to give pain medications to coworker’s patients

- Always tired
- Mood swings
- Frequent suggesting narcotics for pts
- Frequent discrepancies
- Odd behavior
- Missing work days
- Not “clear headed”
- Erratic behavior – ups & downs
- Never observed

Question 5, “What happens to your RN coworker if you report him/her for suspected on-the-job impairment?”, was designed to assess the perceptions of reporting a suspected impaired coworker. Table 5 detailed the frequencies and percentages of responses.

The most frequently selected response (n = 23, 85.19%) was “Required entry to treatment program.” The least commonly selected item was “Public exposure” (n = 7, 25.93%). Two participants wrote in additional information under survey item 5. One wrote “If they are abusing” after the response “Required entry into treatment program.” A second respondent wrote in “Investigation then” before the response “Loss of job.”

Table 5
Frequency Table for Distribution of Responses for Question 5

Variable	<i>n</i>	%
Loss of License		
Yes	11	40.74
Missing	1	3.70
Loss of Job		
Yes	16	59.26
Missing	1	3.70
Public Embarrassment		
Yes	10	37.04
Missing	1	3.70
Public Exposure (Loss of Confidentiality)		
Yes	7	25.93
Missing	1	3.70
Required Entry to Treatment Program		
Yes	23	85.19
Missing	1	3.70

Note. Due to rounding errors, percentages may not equal 100%.

To evaluate whether statistically significant relationships existed within and between the demographic information and survey item responses, a Chi-square Test of Independence was conducted. A Chi-square Test of Independence is commonly used to determine whether a statistically significant relationship exists between two categorical variables (McHugh, 2013). A Chi-square coefficient (χ^2) is used in conjunction with the degrees of freedom (*df*) to obtain a p-value and an alpha of 0.05 is used to assess statistical significance (McHugh, 2013). Because of the small sample size, binary logistic regression was not appropriate.

The results of the Chi-square tests were not significant when examining the majority of relationships between basic participant demographic information, survey

response answers, and comparison between demographic information and individual survey responses. When evaluating years worked and self-perceived ability to identify an impaired coworker as independent measures, no statistically significant relation exists between those two variables (see Table 6). This suggests that these variables are independent of each other and that the observed frequencies were not different from the expected.

Table 6

Frequencies for Years Worked and Ability to Identify Impaired Coworker

Years Worked	Ability to Identify Impaired Coworker		χ^2	<i>df</i>	<i>p</i>
	Yes	No			
0 – 5 Years	9[9.15]	4[3.85]	0.02	1	.901
6 or More Years	10[9.85]	4[4.15]			

Note. Values formatted as Observed [Expected].

When evaluating Employment Status and each participant's ability to identify major risk factors for SUD, a Chi-square Test of Independence was conducted. The results were statistically significant ($\chi^2(1) = 7.56, p = .006$), suggesting that Employment Status and ability to identify major risk factors associated with SUD are related. Table 7 details the results of the Chi-square Test of Independence. More part-time and per diem employees (7) were able to identify 4 or more risk factors compared to the expected (3.89).

Table 7

Frequencies for Employment Status and Major Risk Factors

Employment Status	Identify Major Risk Factors of SUD		χ^2	df	p
	0 - 3	4 or More			
Full-Time	12[8.89]	8[11.11]	7.56	1	.006
Part-Time & Per Diem	0[3.11]	7[3.89]			

Note. Values formatted as Observed [Expected].

To determine whether a significant relationship existed between the respondents who answered “Yes” (Question 3 taken from the survey in Appendix B) when asked if they could identify an impaired coworker and the number of observed behaviors of an impaired coworker identified (Question 4), a Chi-square Test of Independence was conducted. The results of the Chi-square were statistically significant ($\chi^2(1) = 4.89, p = .027$), suggesting that a relationship exists between the two variables. Table 8 illustrates the observed versus expected values when comparing these two variables.

Table 8

Frequencies for Ability to Identify Impaired Coworker and Observed Behaviors

Ability to Identify Impaired Coworker	Observed Behaviors		χ^2	df	p
	0 – 3	4 or More			
Yes	7[9.50]	12[9.50]	4.89	1	.027
No or Unsure	6[3.50]	1[3.50]			

Note. Values formatted as Observed [Expected].

In essence, individuals who perceived that they could identify an impaired coworker were also able to successfully select four or more observable behaviors of RN

impairment (12 observed versus 9.50 expected). Those participants who stated “No” or “Unsure” tended to also select 0 to 3 observable behaviors (6 observed, versus 3.50 expected). More notably, participants who stated that they could not identify an impaired coworker made up almost 30% of the survey respondents ($n = 8$).

DISCUSSION

The initial hypothesis was that survey participants would not be able to correctly identify what happens to an RN colleague once he/she is reported for on-the-job impairment. Table 5 details the frequencies and percentages of the responses to this question. While most participants ($n = 23$, 85.19%) correctly identified that the RN would be required to enter an ATD program, almost 60% of the respondents believed that the RN would lose his/her job. Furthermore, 41% ($n = 11$) perceived that reporting an impaired RN could result in loss of license and 37% ($n = 10$) believed that the RN would suffer public embarrassment. Bettinardi-Angres and Bologeorges (2011) found that most nurses in their study (57%) were reluctant to report a suspected impaired colleague because they did not want to feel responsible for the colleague's loss of job or were insecure about their ability to correctly identify the observed behaviors of SUD.

The majority of the RNs who stated that they could identify an impaired coworker could indeed successfully select observable behaviors of impairment, while those who weren't confident in their abilities could only select a few behaviors. This observation becomes more significant when compared to the fact that eight out of 27 participants stated that they could not successfully detect an impaired colleague. These ED nurses are specifically trained to identify suspected drug or alcohol use in patients, yet falter when asked to do so with an impaired coworker. The RNs surveyed in this project demonstrated a statistically significant chi-square correlation when evaluating nurses who believed they could identify an impaired coworker and their ability to correctly identify observed behaviors or an impaired colleague (see Table 8). No prior research could be found to strengthen this finding, but many studies examined the RN's insecurity in

identifying observable behaviors indicative of SUD (Bettinardi-Angres & Bologeorges, 2011; Cadiz et al., 2017; Kunyk, 2015).

For this project, local statistics of SUD in the ED where the survey was administered were also explored. Within the past five years, two RNs were caught diverting controlled substances and found to be impaired while working. Because both of the RNs worked the cross shift, data analysis was performed to evaluate whether RN participants who worked the cross shift would be more likely to self-identify as able to recognize an impaired coworker, given their recent experience. Table 9 outlines the Chi-square analysis which resulted that this relationship was not statistically significant ($p = .209$). Cross and night shifts are identified in the literature as being at higher risk of attracting nurses with SUD because of limited supervision and ease of access to controlled substances (Kunyk, 2015; Nutty, 2014; Monroe et al., 2015).

Table 9

Frequencies of Shift Worked to Ability to Identify Impaired Coworker

Shift Worked	Ability to Identify Impaired Coworker		χ^2	<i>df</i>	<i>p</i>
	Yes	No			
AM	6[7.31]	4[2.69]	3.13	2	.209
PM	7[7.31]	3[2.69]			
Cross/Split Shift	6[4.38]	0[1.62]			

Note. Values formatted as Observed [Expected].

Compared to full-time employees, part-time and per diem employees identified more risk factors associated with SUD (see Table 7). This could be because these RNs may have other jobs in a variety of settings with increased exposure to SUD. Part-time or

per diem RNs may subsequently have more familiarity or exposure to SUD or SUD education. Another possible explanation for these findings is that full-time employees are more unlikely or unwilling to recognize or identify risk factors because of the cognitive dissonance of accepting that coworkers at their full-time employment may have an increased risk of SUD. Denial is a prevalent concept within substance abuse and dependence, not only of the impaired individual, but of their family and colleagues (ENA, 2016; Lala et al., 2016; SAMSHA, 2019). Nurses who work full-time in the ED may be more personally invested in the culture of the unit and demonstrate increased denial compared to RNs who work less frequently and may be less personally invested.

Ross et al. (2017) and Monroe and Kenaga (2011) described a culture of silence where, in the belief that they are protecting another RN, nurses choose not to report potential or real dangers or violations made by other nurses in the workplace. The concept of a culture of silence does not fully explain the discrepancy between part-time and per diem nurses versus full-time RNs responses. If these findings could be attributed to a culture of silence within nursing, then expected findings would be that neither full-time nor part-time/per diem RNs would identify risk factors of SUD.

In total, almost half of the participants in this survey perceived that nursing SUD prevalence is higher than the accepted rates. This may be because of personal experience or exposure to coworkers with SUD. Several studies (Darbro & Driscoll, 2013; Kunyk, 2015; Lala et al., 2016; Nutty, 2014; Ross et al., 2017) cite nursing burnout, stress, and lack of workplace support as contributors to increased burnout specifically in the ED. This finding contradicts literature that states nurses are more likely to underestimate SUD prevalence rates (Kunyk, 2015; Monroe et al., 2013).

Plan for Evaluation

The five-item survey for this project identified underlying perceptions about SUD as well as knowledge gaps among a specific group of Emergency RNs. The findings of these surveys will be presented to the ED manager and CNO. Two months following the implementation of the targeted educational modules on SUD, another five-item survey will be administered to evaluate the effectiveness of the modules on changing the baseline awareness among a specific group of Emergency RNs.

Educational Program Evaluation

The review of the literature was performed to establish the current statistics regarding SUD among RNs, signs of RN on-the-job impairment, and disciplinary recommendations for RNs with SUD. The review of literature will be used in conjunction with survey data and analysis to guide the refinement of an educational module and recommendations for ongoing focus on SUD (see Appendix I). Post-education assessment and evaluation will guide any necessary refinement to the educational module. The module will reference hospital-specific policies, which is referenced in Appendix J. The data analysis of the post-education surveys will be compared to these initial survey results to identify misconceptions or persisting perceptions among the Emergency RNs and inform future revisions of the educational module. To ensure sustainability, the educational module will be assimilated into the mandatory yearly competency skills fair and will be added for any onboarding Emergency RNs during their department orientation.

The survey results will be compared to the review of literature to identify gaps in knowledge. In coordination with the Director of Education, an educational module will

be created based upon current recommendations as well as gaps in knowledge identified from the survey analysis. Formal approval for the educational module will be obtained from the ED manager and Director of Education. Upon approval, the module will be presented to Emergency RNs through an online portal for mandatory competency training. Evaluation of knowledge retention and/or change in perceptions of SUD in the four categories above will occur using a five-item survey approximately two months following the educational module.

Limitations

The small sample size and single-unit survey participant selection may skew results and limit generalizability. Statistical significance would be improved with an increased sample size. While the ability to free-write answers for survey items was chosen to encourage open answers, without being able to gather more subjective data, interpretation of written-in answers was challenging and open to researcher bias, and therefore not analyzed for this project. Future surveys would benefit through developing and administering surveys using continuous variables such as a Likert scale. This could bolster the data analysis and statistically significant findings. Recency effect could alter participant responses as well. The fact that two RNs had been discovered and disciplined within this specific unit could augment participant responses and limit generalizability.

Recommendations

The 2015 American Nurses Association's (ANA) *Code of Ethics for Nurses* recommends that each RN has an ethical obligation of reporting suspected SUD, yet many nurses report a lack of confidence in ability to correctly identify observed behaviors of SUD (Bettinardi-Angres & Bologeorges, 2011; Cadiz et al., 2017; Kunyk,

2015). On-going RN education is necessary, not only to remind nurses of the incidence and risk factors of SUD among RNs, but to further empower RNs in identifying coworkers who are impaired (Cadiz et al., 2017; Cares et al., 2015; Kunyk, 2015, Monroe & Kenaga, 2011).

The ANA (2015) requires that nurses advocate for impaired colleagues to ensure they receive appropriate treatment. The workplace must also have protocol in place to guide the reporting and intervention process when dealing with suspected SUD (Bettinardi-Angres & Bologeorges, 2011). While nurses are often considered compassionate providers, research indicates RNs frequently view impaired nursing colleagues with less compassion than a patient with SUD (Ross et al., 2017; Monroe & Kenaga, 2011). Protocol should protect the RN with SUD and foster compassionate treatment, guidance, and support. The ANA (2019) and ENA (2016) recommend an ATD program for RNs with SUD, and protocol should be in place to encourage early identification and intervention, thereby minimizing the potential negative impact an impaired RN could have on patient care. Once a protocol is in place, staff should be routinely educated as to the severity, observed behaviors, and protocol for reporting SUD.

Given the risks to patient safety and implications for the nursing practice, SUD should be at the forefront of discussions within the profession, both in the clinical and academic settings. Nursing students should be aware and educated as to the risk factors, implications, and resources available for individuals affected by SUD. Ongoing research is needed in the area of SUD among RNs. Further investigation into whether differences

exist between full-time RNs and non-full-time RNs when it comes to perceptions SUD is necessary.

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APPENDIX A

TABLE OF EVIDENCE

Substance Abuse in Nursing

Purpose (References)	Design & Key Variables	Sample & Setting	Measurements	Results	Author Conclusions, Limitations & Notes
To assess prevalence, common drugs of abuse, demographics, outcomes, & preventative measures for SRNAs with SA. (Bozimowski et al., 2014)*	Cross-sectional, retrospective study: Electronic survey sent to 113 program directors of accredited CRNA schools in US from 2008-2011. Started with lit review of SA in SRNAs & CRNAs studies from 1990 – 2013 IRB approval obtained - Implied informed consent	Electronic survey sent to 113 program (111 responded, representing 2,439 students) directors of US CRNA schools Used faculty recall of reported student SA over past 5 yrs	Used term <i>substance misuse</i> (defined by Bell et al., 1999) Survey items measured: - Period prevalence (incidents/admitted students) - Demographic data - How incident was identified - Existing detection processes to prevention & detection Survey based on previous published surveys (Wischmeyer et al. & Collins et al.)	111 programs participated - 2,439 students (21.7% completed data) with 42.3% response to open-ended screening/prevention strategies ↑ # of females, white & 20-29 yrs with 13-24 mos of SRNA training, ↑ proportion of males Drug of choice = opioids, ETOH, cannabis, benzos, cocaine, polydrug	↓ SRNAs compared to CRNAs (in previous studies) - Prior study (Bell et al.) used self-reporting, so not easily compared to 5 yr faculty recall - Current screening not sufficient (most rely on background check or positive drug test) - Need future research into effective student screening

Purpose (References)	Design & Key Variables	Sample & Setting	Measurements	Results	Author Conclusions, Limitations & Notes
	- Follow-up email 2 wks later - Survey reviewed by 2 researchers			50% had no rx factors, 3 had hx of SA, 3 had fam hx of SA, →most SRNAs enrolled in txt Most background check & drug test (on suspicion)	Limitations: data relies solely on reported incidents (may have ↑ prevalence), poor response rate (21.7%) Note: Included survey questions, graph of specific data, limited to SRNAs (not generalizable?)
To identify behavioral cues of SA, barriers to seeking assistance & strategies for preventing SA by RNs in the workplace.	Qualitative design using anonymous 104-item surveys (with 13 more items attending PHA program for ETOH or drug-use) - series of mailings over 2 months (no names on survey)	Convenience sample of 304 RNs/LPNs via anonymous mail survey to PHA program participants Sampled 441 PHA program participants from	Descriptive data & analysis with frequency distributions & means: (SPSS version OS X for Mac) Fixed response options with “Other” for extra details on most questions	69% response rate (302/441) Demographics detailed SA at work: 25% obtained drugs from work, 48% used at work, 27% put pt at rx	SA can be detected earlier through student & RN education of SA rx & MI rx Recommend RN education of signs of SA, peer support strategies, license

Purpose (References)	Design & Key Variables	Sample & Setting	Measurements	Results	Author Conclusions, Limitations & Notes
(Cares et al., 2015)*	<p>Key variables:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - SA patterns - behavioral cues - perceptions of barriers to help - strategies for preventing/overcoming problem <p>Questions generated/refined through pilot-test group</p> <p>Excluded items: PHA satisfaction & experience \$5 compensation</p>	<p>6/1/2008 – 3/31/2010</p> <p>IRB approval sought – not human subjects research</p>	<p>“Other” responses individually reviewed</p> <p>-Aggregate data from PHA about respondents vs nonrespondents analyzed by Open Epi software (for statistical significance)</p>	<p>68% = early identification possible, 45% reported early physical/emotional change, ↑ absenteeism, ↓ reliability</p> <p>Barriers: fear, embarrassment, concerns for confidentiality, fear for license</p> <p>Help: knowledge of not losing license, support</p>	<p>procedure after SA identification</p> <p>Limitations: Self-report (recall or response bias), survey items generated by study investigators (not exhaustive), limited sample from one program/one region (limited generalizability)</p> <p>Notes: Included tables with survey questions, discusses multiple facets of SA → ideas for projects? most references > 15 yrs old</p>

Purpose (References)	Design & Key Variables	Sample & Setting	Measurements	Results	Author Conclusions, Limitations & Notes
To discuss statistics, demographics, & txt modalities for SUD among RNs (in KY) (Ivey, 2015)	Editorial discussion of SUD, statistics & txt modalities	- provided to RNs in KY with local recommendations for reporting & BON	Informal lit review	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - ↑ prevalence among young, female RNs with little experience - 82% RNs with SUD have not notified employers (Kunyk,2015) & 53% felt that no help would occur if they disclose - cites that 20% of RNs have SUD (Monroe & Kenaga) - of RNs with SUD, 60% have coexisting MI 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Suggested txt: opioid agonist (suboxone, buprenorphine, methadone), pain management, & psychotherapy - Coworkers hold the bulk of the responsibility of reporting suspected intoxicated RNs - Discusses PAP as well as ATD - Brief discussion of KY's BON-approved ATD program (KARE) <p>Notes: provides actual dx of SUD through DSM-V, great references</p>

Purpose (References)	Design & Key Variables	Sample & Setting	Measurements	Results	Author Conclusions, Limitations & Notes
To investigate prevalence of SA, impaired practice, RN perception of SA & organization support (Kunyk, 2015) *	Quantitative evaluation of 12-month retrospective 173-question electronic survey (response rate of 20%) from 2/2010 – 5/2010 - Ethical approval Power analysis for sample size Excluded 172 for neg ETOH use & 1931 for neg drug use Used 5 external content experts to review survey instrument for validity & completeness Used 7 volunteer RNs for survey directions,	Convenience sample of 4,064 RNs, NPs, IP holders & temporary license holders responded to internet survey (no students) - Distributed 15,222 emails Recruited through email, newsletters & Facebook - Minimal demographics gathered & enabled unique psswd to encourage participation - Possible to complete electronically or mail hard copy	University of Alberta's Population Research Laboratory performed survey administration & secure data collection The Survey System Version 10 survey instrument used for transcription Used SF-12v12 Health Survey to calculate mental health & physical health summary measures Used AUDADIS-IV to generate self-rated 12-mo prevalence Used Statistical Package for Social Sciences 19 for data analysis (ANOVA &	Study population representative sample (through demo info analysis) 3% RNs self-identified as SA with 3/121 currently reported by employers, 77.8% had not sought help because "too embarrassed" & "don't think anyone could help" – 50% tested pos for MI 91.5% of RNs with SD currently employed with 97.5% not known by employer RN's uncertain of ability to recognize impaired peers & majority believe SD is	Discipline not considered effective for mitigating pt safety rx of SA-related impaired RN practice Need for management to create safe environ, create effective policies with ATD programs, ↑ trust & atmosphere for reporting Limitations: Study was convenience sample in Alberta (generalizability?), possible inaccurate self-response because of

Purpose (References)	Design & Key Variables	Sample & Setting	Measurements	Results	Author Conclusions, Limitations & Notes
	appearance, readability & flow & 25 volunteer RNs for pilot-testing - Likert-type scale for most questions	- Implied informed consent	MANOVA for continuous variables)	treatable disease & should have confidentiality	stigma/sensitive nature Notes: Included CI & p-value, found link between smoking, depression & SA (used SUD as acronym)
To quantify overall stress, perceived workload, & coping (perceived self- efficacy) among ED (Lala et al., 2016)*	Cross-sectional survey of 366 ED staff members - data recovery with Google forms through email - mandatory answer for each survey item - surveys sent by email with 10-day turnaround cutoff	366 ED staff members sampled (MDs, residents, RNs, aides) Emailed out to ED personnel of Four hospitals in Moselle Dept of Eastern France	Used Perceived Stress Scale PSS-10 - 10-unit questionnaire Brief COPE questionnaire - 14 scales (rated 1-4) for sum total - built from Lazarus' transactional model of stress & Carver & Scheier self-regulation model -obtained basic demographics	- response rate of 50.2% (n = n = 184) - avg subject age = 33 yrs – no statistical diff between genders - wide variation of work hrs b/w professions - ↑ stress scores correlated to perceived work overload (MDs ↑stress, RNs & interns = higher than avg stress)	Perceived work overload & stress is strongly related to work hrs (with ↑ influence on MDs) - Need regular evaluation of stress & stress- related factors as perceived by ED staff - medical interns have ↑ use of substance abuse as coping

Purpose (References)	Design & Key Variables	Sample & Setting	Measurements	Results	Author Conclusions, Limitations & Notes
	-bivariate & multivariate regression models (Excel & SPSS software) - no discussion of IRB			Workload = associati on b/w hrs worked, ED crowding, pt acuity, staff skill & interaction quality <u>Coping Mechanisms</u> - MDs use active coping & planning - RNs use active coping, venting & positive reinterpretation	Limitations: small sample within limited geographic proximity Notes: Looked at MDs, RNs & aides in ED. MDs & interns had ↑ work hours expectation v RNs & aides (skewed results?) Did not include survey items or breakdown of results other than discussion
To estimate one- yr prevalence of RNs needing ATD using state BON data and also compare general	Balanced, stratified sampling design, assessing 2009 annual reports of ATD programs & 2008 National	Evaluated 2009 data for ATD program referral from 59 member boards (avg of 128 RNs/yr) with avg of 41	- used NSDUH data (2009) for estimates of gen pop drug use prevalence - used NCSBN survey (2010) of BON	- Rx factors: access, crit care, job-related stress, depression, knowledge of meds, enabling colleagues	- RNs have ↓ rates of SUD than gen pop Limitations: rigor of data was not verified, used

Purpose (References)	Design & Key Variables	Sample & Setting	Measurements	Results	Author Conclusions, Limitations & Notes
disciplinary & ATD enrollment with gen pop percentages (Monroe et al., 2013)	Sample Survey of RNs - sought IRB (granted exemption)	RNs/board/yr in ATD - stratified for even distribution from urban & rural (auxiliary sample = RNs/stat e) divided into 5 RN pop density strata - convenience sample used for ATD eval (only used state stats with ATD programs)	disciplinary actions on RNs for prevalence of ATD & disciplinary programs - used employed RNs (in each pertinent state) as denominator	- rate of SUD among RNs requiring intervention = 0.51% - rate of RNs who reported receiving ATD for drug or ETOH problems = 1.0% ATD programs had 75% more (n = 9,715) new RNs enrolled compared to disciplinary programs (n = 2,345)	convenience sample based on limited ATD programs - “referral” does not mean “attended” - only assessed reported RNs Note: Don’t take into account RNs who are not detected
To examine aspects of fatal drug toxicity in medical practitioners (drug of choice, demographics & relationship of occupation to drug type & intent)	Retrospective cohort study through NCIS database of reported coroner’s cases between 2003 – 2013 in Australia - only included cases no longer under investigation	Australia - Retrospective analysis of reported drug- related deaths of medical practitioners (RNs, paramedics, MDs, pharmacists , psychologists, & veterinarians)	Extracted demographic data (age, sex, occupation, employment status, case of death, intent classification) as well as police summary of circumstance, coroners’ report, autopsy & toxicology reports	- 62.87% RNs - 2/3 were female - highest mortality rate with veterinarians (CI =42.21-58.79) - 50.25% were intentional self-harm - ↑ incidence of mental health issues (46.04%) - avg 37 deaths/yr	- 5 per 1,000 drug-related deaths of healthcare providers - veterinarians & anesthetists highest rates of mortality - ETOH misuse was common

Purpose (References)	Design & Key Variables	Sample & Setting	Measurements	Results	Author Conclusions, Limitations & Notes
(Pilgrim et al., 2017)	- only included people employed at time of death	404 cases reviewed (only included complete files who were currently employed at time of demise)	Chi-squared tests & analysis of coroner reports Primary Outcome = drug type & intent Covariates = occupati on type, mental illness, self-harm Determined health profession by AHPR	- depression was most common mental health diagnosis - most common drugs were antidepressants, opioids & benzos (CI = 81.15-97.07) - 1/5 cases found drugs stolen or prescribed wrongfully from work - correspondence b/w drug type & occupation	(15%) in tox reports - 1/3 deaths were deemed accidental - substance abuse previously diagnosed in 3% of cases - recommend random drug testing & drug- rehabilitation programs Limitations: only included complete reports that were no longer under investigation (may be higher prevalence) Note: Majority were female & nurses who were still working!

Purpose (References)	Design & Key Variables	Sample & Setting	Measurements	Results	Author Conclusions, Limitations & Notes
					Stress & depression were commonly reported
To establish a Joint Position Statement to create awareness, guide practice & disciplinary recommendation s - 2017 Joint Position Statement of ENA & IntNSA (Strobbe & Crowley, 2017) *	Position statement to establish baseline stats, rx factors, and recommendations from two professional nursing orgs (ENA & IntNSA) as accepted by these orgs	Current literature review – article is targeted to Emergency Nurses	Used statistics from CMS, CDC, & DHHS for baseline pop data	Prevalence = 10% minimum Rx factors = fam hx, stress, depression, access, knowledge of meds, perceived invulnerability Nursing students at rx Discuss bio-psycho- social-spiritual model v “moral or criminal model”	Authors recommend: -education to RNs on drug/ETOH use -create policies, procedures to promote safety -Nursing schools & facilities adopt ATD approach (instead of disciplinary) -View diversion as symptom, not exclusively criminal behavior -Increased awareness among RNs & student RNs with mandatory reporting

Purpose (References)	Design & Key Variables	Sample & Setting	Measurements	Results	Author Conclusions, Limitations & Notes
<p>To discuss current statistics, risk factors, and recommendations for SUD in RNs</p> <p>(Worley, 2017)*</p>	<p>- editorial discussion of SUD among RNs, ATD programs</p>	<p>N/A</p> <p>Uses Kaiser Family Foundation (2017) statistics for current RN estimates & demographics</p>	<p>N/A</p> <p>- informal lit review of current research to eval SUD rx, statistics,</p>	<p>- Females are ↑ rx of overdose & fast-progressing dependency (make up 83% of RNs)</p> <p>- Common themes: Guilt, shame, invulnerability, need for control, poor coping</p> <p>- Early detection is essential</p>	<p>Note: Incredible resource for my project – breaks down into rxs, stats, recommendations (great reference list – double check with my references)</p> <p>- RN schools should be first screeners (non-punitive process to encourage self-report)</p> <p>- Need standardized ATD tx program between States</p> <p>- Need ATD programs <i>outside</i> of the BON</p> <p>Notes: Excellent references</p>

Purpose (References)	Design & Key Variables	Sample & Setting	Measurements	Results	Author Conclusions, Limitations & Notes (current & credible)
<p><i>Note.</i> AHPRA = Australian Health Practitioners Regulatory Agency, benzo = benzodiazepine, BON = Board of Nursing, BRN = Board of Registered Nursing, CDC = Centers for Disease Control and Prevention, CMS = Centers for Medicare and Medicaid Services, CI = confidence interval, CRNA = certified registered nurse anesthetists, demo = demographic, DHHS = Department of Health and Human Services, ETOH = alcohol, gen = general, info = information, IP = interim permit, KARE = Kentucky Alternative Recovery Effect, LPN = licensed practical nurse, mo = month, MI = mental illness, NCIS = National Coronial Information System, NCSBN = National Council of State Boards of Nursing, neg = negative, NP = nurse practitioner, NSDUH = National Survey on Drug Use and Health data, OR = odds ratio, PAP = peer assistance program, PHA = peer health assistance, pop = population, pos = positive, psswd = password, pt = patient, RN = registered nurse, Rx = risk, SA = substance abuse, SRNA = student registered nurse anesthetist, stats = statistics, SUD = substance use disorder, tox = toxicology, txt = treatment, wk = week, yr = year</p> <p>* - Article used in multiple TOEs for cross-TOE content</p>					

Risk Factors for Substance Abuse in Nursing

Purpose (References)	Design & Key Variables	Sample & Setting	Measurements	Results	Author Conclusions, Limitations & Notes
To assess prevalence, common drugs of abuse, demographics, outcomes, & preventative	Cross-sectional, retrospective study: Electronic survey sent to 113 program	Electronic survey sent to 113 program (111 responded, representing 2,439 students)	Used term <i>substance misuse</i> (defined by Bell et al., 1999) Survey items measured:	111 programs participated - 2,439 students (21.7% completed data) with 42.3% response to open-ended	↓ SRNAs compared to CRNAs (in previous studies) Prior study (Bell et al.) used self-reporting, so

Purpose (References)	Design & Key Variables	Sample & Setting	Measurements	Results	Author Conclusions, Limitations & Notes
measures for SRNAs with SA. (Bozimowski et al., 2014)*	<p>directors of accredited CRNA schools in US from 2008-2011.</p> <p>Started with lit review of SA in SRNAs & CRNAs studies from 1990 – 2013</p> <p>IRB approval obtained</p> <p>- Implied informed consent</p> <p>- Follow-up email 2 wks later</p> <p>- Survey reviewed by 2 researchers</p>	<p>directors of US CRNA schools</p> <p>Used faculty recall of reported student SA over past 5 yrs</p>	<p>- Period prevalence (incidents/admitted students)</p> <p>- Demographic data</p> <p>- How incident was identified</p> <p>- Existing detection processes to prevention & detection</p> <p>Survey based on previous published surveys (Wischneyer et al. & Collins et al.)</p>	<p>screening/prevention strategies</p> <p>↑ # of females, white & 20-29 yrs with 13-24 mos of SRNA training, ↑ proportion of males</p> <p>Drug of choice = opioids, ETOH, cannabis, benzos, cocaine, polydrug</p> <p>50% had no rx factors, 3 had hx of SA, 3 had fam hx of SA, →most SRNAs enrolled in txt</p> <p>Most background check & drug test (on suspicion)</p>	<p>not easily compared to 5 yr faculty recall</p> <p>Current screening not sufficient (most rely on background check or positive drug test)</p> <p>Need future research into effective student screening</p> <p>Limitations: data relies solely on reported incidents (may have ↑ prevalence), poor response rate (21.7%)</p> <p>Note: Included survey questions, graph of specific data, limited to SRNAs (not generalizable?)</p>

Purpose (References)	Design & Key Variables	Sample & Setting	Measurements	Results	Author Conclusions, Limitations & Notes
(Cohen dissertation)					
To discuss risk factors of SUD as well as protective factors to promote recover & early identification of RNs with SUD	Editorial discussion of rx factors & protective factors for RNs with SUD by Missouri State BON	No discussion of location or parameters of literature review Targeted toward Missouri RNs	No discussion of measurement data Included adapted model to explain & predict SUD behaviors, rx factors, & protective factors (modified epidemiologic triad-host model)	General rx factors: - psychiatric (depression, anxiety, stress, verbal, sexual abuse) - behavioral (conduct disorder, antisocial personality, rx taking, alienation, recklessness, poor interpersonal skills) - social (early age at first use, social/cultural norms, access) - demographic (male, rural, ↓ income, unemployment - family (ETOH use by family members, poor parenting, death, divorce) - genetic (↓ serotonin, inherited	Bring up self-medication for pain (esp chronic pain) Recommend: - 12-step programs - random urine drug screens - close eval of txt & med - immediate attention to compulsive behavior - inclusion of fam - support - regular assessment for rx factors among staff Limitations: No discussion of rigorous review of lit Notes: Interesting assessment model (epidemiologic) –
(Darbro & Malliarakis, 2013)					

Purpose (References)	Design & Key Variables	Sample & Setting	Measurements	Results	Author Conclusions, Limitations & Notes
				to drug/ETOH dependence) <u>Workplace Factors:</u> - access - stress - ↓ education - attitude	great discussion of prevalent rx factors & recommendations
To explore relationship between length of probation for RNs in Arkansas with SUD violations & recidivism (Davis et al., 2014)	Retrospective study of secondary data analysis of demographic info & data of RN substance use violation & recidivism - Obtained IRB approval from Union University in Jackson, TN & the Arkansas BON	Arkansas BON computer files (GLSuite) of RNs with SUD-related disciplinary probation from 1/1/70-6/30/13: Group 1 (control): 76 RNs with only 1 SUD disciplinary probation Group 2: 76 RNs with 2 or more SUD disciplinary probations	<i>SUD</i> (per DSM-V) – “habitually intemperate or addicted” where substance use interferes with ability to practice nursing <i>Addiction</i> (per ASAM) – chronic disease of brain reward, chronic disease <i>Felony</i> (per ASBN) = violation of UCSB <i>Probation</i> = limit/restriction of aspect of practice (limits on role, setting activity, or hours) <i>Recidivism</i> = new violations after probation - Two-tailed logistic regression model with binary response variable (recidivism v	Most RNs were white (81.6%) & female (85.5%) - ↑ percent male RNs with recidivism (23.7%) - Most RNs were employed in hospital setting (81.6% & 71.1%) - Most RNs were ADNs (57.9% & 61.8%) at first violation - no stat significance between LOP & recidivism No standard disciplinary action between BONs - FL BON withdraws RN	Odds of recidivism for RNs with felony substance convictions = 4.6 x ↑ than RNs without (p<.05) Odds of recidivism for RNs with both drug & ETOH = 5.9 x ↑ - Do not support allowing individuals with past felony convictions to sit for NCLEX - Need more research & replication of study Limitations: Some RNs did not complete probation because of violation/move/retirement

Purpose (References)	Design & Key Variables	Sample & Setting	Measurements	Results	Author Conclusions, Limitations & Notes
			nonrecidivism) odds ration effect size of 1.8, alpha 0.05 & sample power lvl of 0.80 - Chi-square stats, Pearson correlations & sample t-test for demo variables	license if violate 3 separate occasions - Most involved habit-forming drugs (86.8% & 76.3%) - stat significance between use & recidivism if RN used habit-forming & ETOH (13/16)	Notes: add “repeat offenses” as topic? No discussion of dual diagnosis with these stats, limited to Arkansas (generalizable in CA?)
To quantify overall stress, perceived workload, & coping (perceived self- efficacy) among ED (Lala et al., 2016) *	Cross-sectional survey of 366 ED staff members - data recovery with Google forms through email - mandatory answer for each survey item - surveys sent by email with 10- day turnaround cutoff	366 ED staff members sampled (MDs, residents, RNs, aides) Emailed out to ED personnel of Four hospitals in Moselle Dept of Eastern France	Used Perceived Stress Scale PSS-10 - 10-unit questionnaire Brief COPE questionnaire - 14 scales (rated 1-4) for sum total - built from Lazarus’ transactional model of stress & Carver & Scheier self-regulation model -obtained basic demographics	- response rate of 50.2% (n = 184) - avg subject age = 33 yrs – no statistical diff between genders - wide variation of work hrs b/w professions - ↑ stress scores correlated to perceived work overload (MDs ↑stress, RNs & interns = higher than avg stress)	Perceived work overload & stress is strongly related to work hrs (with ↑ influence on MDs) - Need regular evaluation of stress & stress-related factors as perceived by ED staff - medical interns have ↑ use of substance abuse as coping Limitations: small sample within limited geographic proximity

Purpose (References)	Design & Key Variables	Sample & Setting	Measurements	Results	Author Conclusions, Limitations & Notes
	-bivariate & multivariate regression models (Excel & SPSS software) - no discussion of IRB			Workload = associati on b/w hrs worked, ED crowding, pt acuity, staff skill & interaction quality MDs choose active coping & planning as coping mechanism - RNs use active coping, venting & positive reinterpretation for coping	Notes: Looked at MDs, RNs & aides in ED. MDs & interns had ↑ work hours expectation v RNs & aides (skewed results?) Did not include survey items or breakdown of results other than discussion
To examine perceptions of nursing students of rx factors & protective factors with ETOH use in BSN. (McCulloh et al., 2017)	Qualitative study using community-based participatory research (Photovoice) Goals: a) participant can document environ rx & abuse; b) RN students shared & discussed strengths; c)	Purposive sample of 12 senior-level BSN students at “dry” Philadelphia campus (of 14,000 undergraduates) - Recruited through peer invitation, classroom announcements, & univ online learning system	Screened ETOH use/abuse with AUDIT-C (good at identifying hazard drinkers & ETOH use disorder) Study participants analyzed and grouped data Thematic content analysis through NVivo software (images, individual/group	- RN students have ↑ drinking ↑ rx of witnessing life/death, irregular schedules, intense interpersonal relationships, burnout Identified 3 issues: stress, environmental influence, societal acceptance & conveniences Rx Factors:	RN students created ppt & presented findings - Rx & protective factors categorized according to multi-level of influence in SEM - Found indoctrination to ETOH & drugs - BSN students learn drinking is “norm” - dry campus ↑ rx & stealth

Purpose (References)	Design & Key Variables	Sample & Setting	Measurements	Results	Author Conclusions, Limitations & Notes
	<p>findings change univ policy</p> <p>4 focus groups with semi-structured, open-ended ?s</p> <p>- obtained IRB approval</p> <p>- obtained consent</p> <p>- gave \$50 gift card for participation</p>		<p>reflections, verbatim transcripts)</p> <p>-Used inductive qualitative analyses during group meetings</p> <p>- Used immersion & crystallization to ask ?s of data together</p>	<p>- ↓ \$, nursing major, social environ, Type A personality (perfectionist, competitive, easily frustrated)</p> <p>Protective Factors:</p> <p>- perceived reputation, physical environ, healthy lifestyle & activity, nursing responsibilities</p>	<p>- students mixed ETOH with anti-anxiety/depression meds</p> <p>- limited interaction between freshman & senior BSN students</p> <p>Limitations: mainly white, all female participants (generalizable?)</p> <p>Notes: interesting approach having students analyze & present data, used Ecological Model for Health Promotion (SEM)</p>
<p>To estimate one-yr prevalence of RNs needing ATD using state BON data and also compare general</p>	<p>Balanced, stratified sampling design, assessing 2009 annual reports of ATD programs & 2008 National Sample Survey of RNs</p>	<p>Evaluated 2009 data for ATD program referral from 59 member boards (avg of 128 RNs/yr) with avg of 41 RNs/board/yr in ATD</p>	<p>- used NSDUH data (2009) for estimates of gen pop drug use prevalence</p> <p>- used NCSBN survey (2010) of BON disciplinary actions on RNs for prevalence of</p>	<p>- Rx factors: access, crit care, job-related stress, depression, knowledge of meds, enabling colleagues</p> <p>- rate of SUD among RNs requiring intervention = 0.51%</p>	<p>- RNs have ↓ rates of SUD than gen pop</p> <p>Limitations: rigor of data was not verified, used convenience sample based on limited ATD programs</p>

Purpose (References)	Design & Key Variables	Sample & Setting	Measurements	Results	Author Conclusions, Limitations & Notes
disciplinary & ATD enrollment with gen pop percentages (Monroe et al., 2013)	- sought IRB (granted exemption)	- stratified for even distribution from urban & rural (auxiliary sample = RNs/sta te) divided into 5 RN pop density strata - convenience sample used for ATD eval (only used state stats with ATD programs)	ATD & disciplinary programs - used employed RNs (in each pertinent state) as denominator	- rate of RNs who reported receiving ATD for drug or ETOH problems = 1.0% ATD programs had 75% more (n = 9,715) new RNs enrolled compared to disciplinary programs (n = 2,345)	- "referral" does not mean "attended" - only assessed reported RNs Note: Don't take into account RNs who are not detected
To discuss the statistics, rxs, signs, and recommendatio ns for SUD in Alaska nurses. (Nutty, 2014) *	Editorial review of SUD, rx factors, signs, & recommendation s through lit review	Targeted towards Alaska Nurses (publication from Alaska Nurses Association)	Vague review of literature	6-8 % of RNs use substances enough to disrupt practice Rx: stress in ED & ICU (↑ rx with ↑ acuity), night & variable shift workers, ↑ rates of injury & emotional trauma, access - Alaska doesn't have ATD (5 yrs probation, abstinence, NA/AA	Impaired RNs are Significant rx to pt safety (↑ injuries, ↑ errors) - RNs are ethically bound to report - treat colleagues with compassion Recognizes SUD as chronic, progressive, preventable brain disease (but still has stigma)

Purpose (References)	Design & Key Variables	Sample & Setting	Measurements	Results	Author Conclusions, Limitations & Notes
				meetings, public announcement Warning Signs: - ↓ hygiene - ↓ pt pain control - frequent bathroom breaks - offers to medicate pt ↑ med errors ↑ narc sign-out - frequent tardies - sloppy record-keeping - isolation from colleagues	>80% of BONs have ATD programs Note: Estimates 10-15% Note: discusses Alaska's specific non-ATD program, briefly discusses the ethical need to report
To examine aspects of fatal drug toxicity in medical practitioners (drug of choice, demographics & relationship of occupation to drug type & intent)	Retrospective cohort study through NCIS database of reported coroner's cases between 2003 – 2013 in Australia - only included cases no longer	Australia - Retrospective analysis of reported drug-related deaths of medical practitioners (RNs, paramedics, MDs, pharmacists, psychologists, & veterinarians)	Extracted demographic data (age, sex, occupation, employment status, case of death, intent classification) as well as police summary of circumstance, coroners' report, autopsy & toxicology reports Chi-squared tests & analysis of coroner reports	- 62.87% RNs - 2/3 were female - highest mortality rate with veterinarians (CI =42.21-58.79) - 50.25% were intentional self-harm - ↑ incidence of mental health issues (46.04%) - avg 37 deaths/yr	- 5 per 1,000 drug-related deaths of healthcare providers - veterinarians & anesthesiologists highest rates of mortality - ETOH misuse was common (15%) in tox reports - 1/3 deaths were deemed accidental

Purpose (References)	Design & Key Variables	Sample & Setting	Measurements	Results	Author Conclusions, Limitations & Notes
(Pilgrim et al., 2017)	under investigation - only included people employed at time of death	404 cases reviewed (only included complete files who were currently employed at time of demise)	Primary Outcome = drug type & intent Covariates = occupation type, mental illness, self-harm Determined health profession by AHPR	- depression was most common mental health diagnosis - most common drugs were antidepressants, opioids & benzos (CI = 81.15-97.07) - 1/5 cases found drugs stolen or prescribed wrongfully from work - correspondence b/w drug type & occupation	- substance abuse previously diagnosed in 3% of cases - recommend random drug testing & drug-rehabilitation programs Limitations: only included complete reports that were no longer under investigation (may be higher prevalence) Note: Majority were female & nurses who were still working! Stress & depression were commonly reported
To conduct integrative review of lit to evaluate structural factors that enable PSU instead of	Conduct integrative review of lit: Stage 1: comprehensive lit search on PSU (English lang, after 1980)	Did not reveal databases Stage 1: 714 unique records Stage 2: 74 records yielded 3 themes, then researchers added 5 more	Structural factors = operationalized def from Rhodes, 2002 study (didn't provide exact def) Risk environment model = environment is	Major themes: stress, access, attitude, txt policies, culture of RN profession - RNs may NOT have ↑ PSU (v general pop)	Punitive policies responsible for ↓ reporting & ↑ silence → recommend ATD Culture of RNs → weakness of character, unsupportive RNs, "culture of silence"

Purpose (References)	Design & Key Variables	Sample & Setting	Measurements	Results	Author Conclusions, Limitations & Notes
individual rx factors (Ross et al., 2017) *	Stage 2: Printed & read every record, developed themes Stage 3: Researched 5 identified themes	Stage 3: applied 5 themes to original 74 records	primary unit of analysis & change	- Access as rx factor is unfounded - Stress (emotional or physical) ↑ rx by 50-60% - men can hide PSU easier - ↑ work stress seen as “reality” of prof - Attitudes – RNs justify PSU with stress & chronic pain - ↑ drug knowledge – RNs have ↑ depression, chronic pain, use of meds - ↑ self-med	→ recommend supportive behavior Limitations – limited discussion on structural factors (as titled in article) Notes: Use PSU instead of SUD, estimate use from 6-20%, incredible systematic review of rx factors with division into intuitive categories
To establish a Joint Position Statement to create awareness, guide practice & disciplinary recommendations - 2017 Joint Position Statement of	Position statement to establish baseline stats, rx factors, and recommendations from two professional nursing orgs (ENA & IntNSA) as	Current literature review – article is targeted to Emergency Nurses	Used statistics from CMS, CDC, & DHHS for baseline pop data	Prevalence = 10% minimum Rx factors = fam hx, stress, depression, access, knowledge of meds, perceived invulnerability Nursing students at rx	Authors recommend: -education to RNs on drug/ETOH use -create policies, procedures to promote safety -Nursing schools & facilities adopt ATD approach (instead of disciplinary) -View diversion as symptom, not

Purpose (References)	Design & Key Variables	Sample & Setting	Measurements	Results	Author Conclusions, Limitations & Notes
ENA & IntNSA (Strobbe & Crowley, 2017) *	accepted by these orgs			Discuss bio-psycho-social-spiritual model v “moral or criminal model”	exclusively criminal behavior -Increased awareness among RNs & student RNs with mandatory reporting Note: Incredible resource for my project – breaks down into rxs, stats, recommendations (great reference list – double check with my references)
To discover association between specific SA within past year and nursing specialty. (Trinkoff & Storr, 1998)	Anonymous, mailed 8-page survey to evaluate SA in past 12 months Collected data: -substance use -working conditions -psychological well-being - lifestyle/behavioral practices	Balanced stratified sampling of US registered nurse population in 10 states (combined probability sampling with model-based) -Random sampling of 6,000 (600 from each state) →4,438	Used adjusted odds ratios to analyze OR for each subset of SA as it relates to specialty Used ‘by hand’ coding when specialties were written in -95% CI constructed around estimates - Outside of cigarettes & ETOH, 1 or more times was definition of “use”	Oncology RNs had ↑ prevalence, then psych, then ED, then ICU -ED & ped ICU had ↑ marijuana/cocaine, then ICU Odds of marijuana/cocaine were 3.5 times ↑ in ED than reference group	Sample was not specifically from RNs in diversion program (included any use, not necessarily abuse or dependence) Increased report of Rx drug use with RNs (compared to general pop) Limitations: did not discuss exclusion criteria, no

Purpose (References)	Design & Key Variables	Sample & Setting	Measurements	Results	Author Conclusions, Limitations & Notes
	<p>Introductory letter, then questionnaire</p> <p>Included 15 specialties with option to write-in (after consulting with 2 clinical nurse experts & manual) & 4 subsets of substance use: marijuana/cocaine, Rx, cigarette, ETOH</p> <p>Adjusted rates for confounding sociodemographic variables</p>	<p>responded (mostly female)</p>	<p>-Discussed sociodemographic composition of specialties & excluded specialties with lowest use (used as reference group)</p> <p>Used regression models with ORs & CIs</p>	<p>SA use in RNs is equal to general pop</p> <p>ICU & ED have ↑ use of marijuana/cocaine, perhaps it coincides with “impulsivity” gene</p> <p>Rates per specialty coincided with reported rates among physician specialties</p>	<p>examination of polydrug, loose definition of “use”</p> <p>Did not discuss specific 10 states polled (generalizability?), no CRNAs</p> <p>Note: Old study, but referenced often in other studies, stratified SA by RN specialty</p>
<p>To discuss current statistics, risk factors, and recommendations</p>	<p>- editorial discussion of SUD among RNs, ATD programs</p>	<p>Uses Kaiser Family Foundation (2017) statistics for current RN</p>	<p>- informal lit review of current research to eval SUD rx, statistics,</p>	<p>- Females are ↑ rx of overdose & fast-progressing dependency (make up 83% of RNs)</p>	<p>- RN schools should be first screeners (non-punitive process to encourage self-report)</p>

Purpose (References)	Design & Key Variables	Sample & Setting	Measurements	Results	Author Conclusions, Limitations & Notes
ns for SUD in RNs (Worley, 2017)*		estimates & demographics		- Common themes: Guilt, shame, invulnerability, need for control, poor coping - Early detection is essential	- Need standardized ATD tx program between States - Need ATD programs <i>outside</i> of the BON Notes: Excellent references (current & credible)

Note. ADN = associate degree in nursing, ASAM = American Society of Addiction Medicine, ASBN = Arkansas State Board of Nursing, benzo = benzodiazepine, BRN = Board of Registered Nursing, BSN = Bachelor of Science in Nursing, CI = confidence interval, CRNA = certified registered nurse anesthetists, def = definition, demo = demographic, environ = environment, ETOH = alcohol, info = information, IP = interim permit, lang = language, lit = literature, LOP = length of probation, LPN = licensed practical nurse, med = medication, MI = mental illness, mo = month, neg = negative, NP = nurse practitioner, OR = odds ratio, PHA = peer health assistance, pop = population, pos = positive, psswd = password, PSU = problematic substance use, pt = patient, RN = registered nurse, Rx = risk, SA = substance abuse, SEM = Sociological Ecological Model, SRNA = student registered nurse anesthetist, stat = statistical, SUD = substance use disorder, txt = treatment, UCSB = Uniform Controlled Substances Act, univ = university, wk = week, yr = year

Barriers to Reporting and Seeking Treatment

Purpose (References)	Design & Key Variables	Sample & Setting	Measurements	Results	Author Conclusions, Limitations & Notes
To identify behavioral cues of SA, barriers to seeking assistance & strategies for preventing SA by RNs in the workplace. (Cares et al., 2015) *	Qualitative design using anonymous 104-item surveys (with 13 more items attending PHA program for ETOH or drug-use) - series of mailings over 2 months (no names on survey) Key variables: - SA patterns - behavioral cues - perceptions of barriers to help - strategies for preventing/overcoming problem Questions generated/refined through pilot-test group	Convenience sample of 304 RNs/LPNs via anonymous mail survey to PHA program participants Sampled 441 PHA program participants from 6/1/2008 – 3/31/2010 IRB approval sought – not human subjects research	Descriptive data & analysis with frequency distributions & means: (SPSS version OS X for Mac) Fixed response options with “Other” for extra details on most questions “Other” responses individually reviewed -Aggregate data from PHA about respondents vs nonrespondents analyzed by Open Epi software (for statistical significance)	69% response rate (302/441) Demographics detailed SA at work: 25% obtained drugs from work, 48% used at work, 27% put pt at rx 68% = early identification possible, 45% reported early physical/emotional change, ↑ absenteeism, ↓ reliability Barriers: fear, embarrassment, concerns for confidentiality, fear for license	SA can be detected earlier through student & RN education of SA rx & MI rx - Recommend RN education of signs of SA, peer support strategies, license procedure after SA identification Limitations: Self-report (recall or response bias), survey items generated by study investigators (not exhaustive), limited sample from one program/one region (limited generalizability) Notes: Included tables with survey questions, discusses

Purpose (References)	Design & Key Variables	Sample & Setting	Measurements	Results	Author Conclusions, Limitations & Notes
	Excluded items: PHA satisfaction & experience \$5 compensation			Help: knowledge of not losing license, support	multiple facets of SA → ideas for projects? most references > 15 yrs old
To conduct integrative review of lit to evaluate structural factors that enable PSU instead of individual rx factors (Ross et al., 2017) *	Conduct integrative review of lit: Stage 1: comprehensive lit search on PSU (English lang, after 1980) Stage 2: Printed & read every record, developed themes Stage 3: Researched 5 identified themes No detail of which authors did what	Did not reveal databases Stage 1: 714 unique records Stage 2: 74 records yielded 3 themes, then researchers added 5 more Stage 3: applied 5 themes to original 74 records	Structural factors = operationalized def from Rhodes, 2002 study (didn't provide exact def) Risk environment model = environment is primary unit of analysis & change	Major themes: stress, access, attitude, txt policies, culture of RN profession - RNs may NOT have ↑ PSU (v general pop) - Access as rx factor is unfounded - Stress (emotional or physical) ↑ rx by 50-60% - men can hide PSU easier - ↑ work stress seen as "reality" of prof - Attitudes – RNs justify PSU with stress & chronic pain - ↑ drug knowledge – RNs have ↑ depression, chronic pain, use of meds - ↑ self-med	Punitive policies responsible for ↓ reporting & ↑ silence → recommend ATD Culture of RNs → weakness of character, unsupportive RNs, "culture of silence" → recommend supportive behavior Limitations – limited discussion on structural factors (as titled in article) - Did not include search terms for systematic review Notes: Use PSU instead of SUD, estimate use from 6- 20%, incredible systematic review of

Purpose (References)	Design & Key Variables	Sample & Setting	Measurements	Results	Author Conclusions, Limitations & Notes
To discuss current statistics, risk factors, and recommendations for SUD in RNs (Worley, 2017)*	- editorial discussion of SUD among RNs, ATD programs	N/A Uses Kaiser Family Foundation (2017) statistics for current RN estimates & demographics	N/A - informal lit review of current research to eval SUD rx, statistics,	- Females are ↑ rx of overdose & fast- progressing dependency (make up 83% of RNs) - Common themes: Guilt, shame, invulnerability, need for control, poor coping - Early detection is essential	rx factors with division into intuitive categories - RN schools should be first screeners (non-punitive process to encourage self-report) - Need standardized ATD tx program between States - Need ATD programs <i>outside</i> of the BON Notes: Excellent references (current & credible)

Note. benzo = benzodiazepine, BRN = Board of Registered Nursing, CI = confidence interval, CRNA = certified registered nurse anesthetists, demo = demographic, ETOH = alcohol, info = information, IP = interim permit, LPN = licensed practical nurse, mo = month, MI = mental illness, neg = negative, NP = nurse practitioner, OR = odds ratio, PHA = peer health assistance, pop = population, pos = positive, psswd = password, pt = patient, RN = registered nurse, Rx = risk, SA = substance abuse, SRNA = student registered nurse anesthetist, SUD = substance use disorder, txt = treatment, wk = week, yr = year

Early Detection and Intervention

Purpose (References)	Design & Key Variables	Sample & Setting	Measurements	Results	Author Conclusions, Limitations & Notes
To describe the creation of a Common Risky Behaviour Checklist tool to help RN supervisors identify SUD in RN staff (Cadiz et al., 2015)	Qualitative surveys to create assessment tool Followed six phases to develop tool: 1. Literature review (3 searches) 2. Critical incident collection & item generation (through 4 focus groups & 1 online survey) 3. Item reduction & categorization (to fit CNA framework) 4. Review by SMEs (via surveys of 4 SMEs & 9 RN managers) 5. Item refinement & tool design 6. RN supervisor review	Incident collection surveys = 4 60-min focus groups (convenience sample of RNs, RN managers, pharmacist, RNs who were enrolled in ATD programs) Anonymous online survey distributed by key individuals in ATD program In total, generated 223 impairment behaviors	Critical Incidence = observable behaviors while RN is under the influence of drugs or ETOH Analyzed data through SPSS	Iterative process revealed 5 categories of behavior: Attendance/Work Pattern Changes, Cognitive Performance, Interpersonal/Social Performance, Physical Performance, Policy Adherence/Drug Diversion Authors conclude that tool is helpful because of rigorous process of creating tool – especially good for urgent assessment & decisions	RN managers are first-line in early identification – no standard tool to help in assessment/decisions Limitations: Did not research sensitivity/specificity of tool, facilities may have P/P that conflicts with their assessment tool, don't know if the tool ↑ RN manager ability to identify SUD (need training?) Notes: Included definitions of each rx behavior

Purpose (References)	Design & Key Variables	Sample & Setting	Measurements	Results	Author Conclusions, Limitations & Notes
	Six-phases occurred from June 2010 – Mar. 2011 - IRB Approval & Informed consent obtained	Portland, OR		Tool provides language that can be used in formal documentation	category, includes the actual tool (can I use it as part of my intervention?)
To investigate prevalence of SA, impaired practice, RN perception of SA & organization support (Kuynk, 2015)*	Quantitative evaluation of 12- month retrospective 173-question electronic survey (response rate of 20%) from 2/2010 – 5/2010 - Ethical approval Power analysis for sample size Excluded 172 for neg ETOH use & 1931 for neg drug use Used 5 external content experts to review survey instrument for validity & completeness	Convenience sample of 4,064 RNs, NPs, IP holders & temporary license holders responded to internet survey (no students) - Distributed 15,222 emails Recruited through email, newsletters & Facebook - Minimal demographics gathered & enabled unique	University of Alberta’s Population Research Laboratory performed survey administration & secure data collection The Survey System Version 10 survey instrument used for transcription Used SF-12v12 Health Survey to calculate mental health & physical health summary measures	Study population representative sample (through demo info analysis) - 3% RNs self- identified as SA with 3/121 currently reported by employers, 77.8% had not sought help because “too embarrassed” & “don’t think anyone could help” – 50% tested pos for MI 91.5% of RNs with SD currently	Discipline not considered effective for mitigating pt safety rx of SA- related impaired RN practice Need for management to create safe environ, create effective policies with ATD programs, ↑ trust & atmosphere for reporting Limitations: Study was convenience sample in Alberta

Purpose (References)	Design & Key Variables	Sample & Setting	Measurements	Results	Author Conclusions, Limitations & Notes
Used 7 volunteer RNs for survey directions, appearance, readability & flow & 25 volunteer RNs for pilot-testing - Likert-type scale for most questions	psswd to encourage participation - Possible to complete electronically or mail hard copy - Implied informed consent	Used AUDADIS-IV to generate self-rated 12-mo prevalence Used Statistical Package for Social Sciences 19 for data analysis (ANOVA & MANOVA for continuous variables)	employed with 97.5% not known by employer RN's uncertain of ability to recognize impaired peers & majority believe SD is treatable disease & should have confidentiality	(generalizability?), possible inaccurate self-response because of stigma/sensitive nature Notes: Included CI & p-value, found link between smoking, depression & SA (used SUD as acronym)	
To discuss the statistics, rxs, signs, and recommendations for SUD in Alaska nurses. (Nutty, 2014) *	Editorial review of SUD, rx factors, signs, & recommendations through lit review	Targeted towards Alaska Nurses (publication from Alaska Nurses Association)	Vague review of literature	6-8 % of RNs use substances enough to disrupt practice Rx: stress in ED & ICU (↑ rx with ↑ acuity), night & variable shift workers, ↑ rates of injury & emotional trauma, access - Alaska doesn't have ATD (5 yrs	Impaired RNs are Significant rx to pt safety (↑injuries, ↑errors) - RNs are ethically bound to report - treat colleagues with compassion Recognizes SUD as chronic, progressive, preventable brain

Purpose (References)	Design & Key Variables	Sample & Setting	Measurements	Results	Author Conclusions, Limitations & Notes
				probation, abstinence, NA/AA meetings, public announcement Warning Signs: - ↓ hygiene - ↓ pt pain control - frequent bathroom breaks - offers to medicate pt ↑ med errors ↑ narc sign-out - frequent tardies - sloppy record- keeping - isolation from colleagues	disease (but still has stigma) >80% of BONs have ATD programs Note: Estimates 10-15% Note: discusses Alaska's specific non-ATD program, briefly discusses the ethical need to report
To create systematic review of outcomes of remediation/rehabilitation programs for healthcare professionals with performance concerns (and explore	Systematic review of Medline, Embase, PsycINFO, & CINAHL) from 1/1/90 – 5/7/17 – English, peer-reviewed articles on outcomes of	Reviewed 38 studies for outcomes of remediation/rehab programs for healthcare workers (dentists,	Used Newcastle-Ottawa Scale for quality assessment Performance problems = symptoms of underlying	57.9% studies were in USA 26.3% in Canada - most (78.9%) evaluated outcomes for MDs and on SUDs (63.2%)	US studies on MDs dominates lit Recommend that ATD programs be created/used Need more studies on difference of outcomes between

Purpose (References)	Design & Key Variables	Sample & Setting	Measurements	Results	Author Conclusions, Limitations & Notes
differences between professions) (Weenink et al., 2017)	remediation/rehabilitat ion programs - excluded conference abstracts & studies focused on students, trainees, or residents - consulted database expert from library for search refinement - 2 authors screened all titles & abstracts (with Rayyan software) - Used reference lists & in-text citations	midwives, RNs, pharmacists, MDs, physiotherapists , psychologist, psychotherapist s) Researchers were in the Netherlands	disorder (mental, physical, behavior) Health Problems = prof who are personally sick, but prof healthy Knowledge & Skills Problems = prof who are personally healthy but prof sick Personal & UnProf Behavior Problems = prof who have problems with prof but no knowledge/skill problems	- ↑ program completion (47.6% & 64%) for RNs - ↑ return to work (74%, 81%, 90%) for RNs - abstinence rates 60-94% for RNs - ↑ sustained recovery (> 2yrs) 94% for RNs - ↓ emotional exhaustion & burnout for RNs - High # of research on MDs recovery programs in US could be secondary to ↑ lawsuits - Overall SUD program completion = 70- 90%	disciplinary action & ATD programs - Positive outcomes include decreased emotional distress & less boundary violations - No valid comparison between professions found Limitations: Did not include grey literature, differences in programs made comparison difficult, individuals with mental issues as well as SUD may skew findings Note: Bulk of the data was on MDs

Purpose (References)	Design & Key Variables	Sample & Setting	Measurements	Results	Author Conclusions, Limitations & Notes
Explore & identify factors promoting recovery of opioid addiction among CRNAs with hx of opioid addiction. (Wright et al, 2014) *	Qualitative research 12 open-ended questions through one-on-one telephone interviews of 6 CRNAs who had returned to work after regulatory action from discovered opioid dependence - IRB approval from University of Alabama - participant anonymity	Convenience sample of 6 CRNAs with hx of opioid dependency, undergone treatment, dealt with regulatory sanctions (not working for 8+ mos), & returned to anesthesiology - obtained sample through online	Successful recovery = sobriety (abstinence of addictive substance) for > 5 yrs (as defined by Betty Ford Foundation Panel) - Used content analysis for systematic, objective categorizing of data	- Outcomes similar between disciplinary & ATD programs Fentanyl was primary drug for 5 - 1 began abuse after injury - 2 reported coexisting mental disorder Avg time of opioid use before entering recover = 2.1 yrs - 5 were caught at work – 1 self-reported <u>Two Factors</u> (identified	(not generalizable to RNs), looks at emotional distress & dysfunctional practice as outcomes (positively impacted by ATD programs) Returning to place with access is challenging Recovery requires deep commitment to recovery process (typically includes AA, NA, &/or counseling) Need trigger management Having facility “take a chance” on participant was crucial

Purpose (References)	Design & Key Variables	Sample & Setting	Measurements	Results	Author Conclusions, Limitations & Notes
		advertisement on Anesthetists in Recovery site - 24 responded, 11 met eligibility criteria, 6 completed consent - semi- structured individual telephone interviews with open-ended ?s		themes) to ↑ recovery: Personal – remove obsession, self- realization, seeing future, inner strength External – talk with others, state involvement, getting a chance, work environ, time	Random urine drug testing was deterrent Limitations: excluded CRNAs who had relapsed – not generalizable to other RNs? Notes: Although focused on CRNAs, perhaps applicable in ED? Need peer support to facilitate sustained recovery
To examine effects of 3-hr mandatory online SUD course on RN knowledge. (Zickafoose, 2018)	Quasi-experimental pretest-posttest after NCSBN online learning course - online, self-paced pre- & posttest (3 wks to complete)	Convenience sample of 86 RNs in Delaware who were due for license renewal by 5/31/15 (68 completed)	Used transformational ethical framework to explain influence of ↑ RN knowledge SUD = (instead of addiction & abuse)	22% (p< 00.1) increase in posttest scores after modules - most frequent lack of knowledge = scien	Mandatory CEs on SUD are effective in educating RNs - Need to retest 68 participants after 6 – 12 mos to assess knowledge retention

Purpose (References)	Design & Key Variables	Sample & Setting	Measurements	Results	Author Conclusions, Limitations & Notes
	- IRB approval obtained from Wilmington University	<p>- original pool was 1,817 with 236 codes emailed to participants to participate in study</p> <p>- Completed 10-item demographic questionnaire & pretest</p> <p>- self-paced online module with e-learning strategies & assignment book with short-answer & essay questions</p>	<p>individual repeatedly uses ETOH, drugs or both & it causes impairment at work, home, or school</p> <p>Used staircase model for professional development to discuss RN “slip” with SUD</p>	<p>ce of SUD & effects on brain, requirements of monitoring programs, txt parameters for SUD</p> <p>RNs age 45-54 had ↑ improvement, RNs with no degree had ↑ score improvement, Surgical RNs had ↑ improvement, RNs with 31-40 yrs experience had ↑ improvement on scores</p>	<p>- More states should adopt this approach to ↑ RN knowledge</p> <p>Notes: Talks about nat data on disciplinary action (Nursys), provides table of SUD signs, gave hypotheses but not actual items, gave link to online modules</p>
		<p>Sample = 1 male, 67 female, most participants were 45 – 54 yrs old</p>			

Note. AA = Alcoholics Anonymous, benzo = benzodiazepine, BRN = Board of Registered Nursing, CI = confidence interval, CNA = Canadian Nurses Association, CRNA = certified registered nurse anesthetists, demo = demographic, ETOH = alcohol, info = information, IP = interim permit, LPN = licensed practical nurse, mo = month, MI = mental illness, NA = Narcotics Anonymous, neg = negative, NCSBN = National Council of State Boards of Nursing, NP = nurse practitioner, OR = odds ratio, PHA = peer health assistance, pop = population, pos = positive, prof = professionally, psswd = password, pt = patient, RN = registered nurse, Rx = risk, SA = substance abuse, SRNA = student registered nurse anesthetist, SUD = substance use disorder, txt = treatment, wk = week, yr = year

APPENDIX B

FIVE-ITEM SURVEY OF PERCEPTIONS OF SUD

Gender:	<input type="checkbox"/> Male	<input type="checkbox"/> Female	<input type="checkbox"/> Other
Employment Status:	<input type="checkbox"/> Full-time	<input type="checkbox"/> Part-time	<input type="checkbox"/> Per diem
Shift Worked:	<input type="checkbox"/> AM	<input type="checkbox"/> PM	<input type="checkbox"/> Cross Shift/Split Shift
Years in ED:	<input type="checkbox"/> 0 – 5 years <input type="checkbox"/> 6 – 10 years <input type="checkbox"/> 11 – 15 years <input type="checkbox"/> 16 – 20 years <input type="checkbox"/> 21 + years		
1. According to the ENA/ANA, out of approximately 3.4 million registered nurses in the U.S. (Kaiser Family Foundation, 2018), how many are reported to have a problem with drugs and or alcohol?	<input type="checkbox"/> 68,000 (2%) <input type="checkbox"/> 170,000 (5%) <input type="checkbox"/> 340,000 (10%) <input type="checkbox"/> 510,000 (15%) <input type="checkbox"/> 680,000 (20%) <input type="checkbox"/> Other, please describe _____ _____ _____		
2. What are the identified major risk factors of Substance Use Disorder (<i>a condition that occurs when recurrent alcohol and/or drug use causes clinically significant impairment</i>) among nurses? Select all that apply.	<input type="checkbox"/> Work Overload <input type="checkbox"/> Stress <input type="checkbox"/> Poor Coping <input type="checkbox"/> Access to medications <input type="checkbox"/> Knowledge of medications <input type="checkbox"/> Depression <input type="checkbox"/> Financial Commitments <input type="checkbox"/> Chronic Pain <input type="checkbox"/> Other, please describe _____ _____ _____		

<p>3. Could you identify a coworker who is impaired because of drug/alcohol use?</p>	<p><input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/> Unsure</p>
<p>4. What are the observable behaviors of an impaired nursing colleague? Select all that apply.</p>	<p><input type="checkbox"/> Takes extended breaks during the shift, sometimes without telling coworkers <input type="checkbox"/> Exhibits aggression/hostility towards patients or coworkers <input type="checkbox"/> Changes in speech <input type="checkbox"/> Reports medication being wasted when it was not <input type="checkbox"/> Colleague's patients consistently complain of pain <input type="checkbox"/> Other, please describe _____ _____ _____</p>
<p>5. What happens to your RN coworker if you report them for suspected on-the-job impairment? Select all that apply.</p>	<p><input type="checkbox"/> Loss of License <input type="checkbox"/> Loss of Job <input type="checkbox"/> Public Embarrassment <input type="checkbox"/> Public Exposure (loss of confidentiality) <input type="checkbox"/> Required Entry to Treatment Program</p>

APPENDIX C**PERMISSION LETTER FROM CARES ET AL.**

June 11, 2018

Hi Kate,

At long last, please find the survey attached. I checked with the professor that I worked with at the time and the person at the organization that we contracted with to do the evaluation (Peer Assistance Services, Inc.) and they requested proper acknowledgment if you use or modify the survey tool. Please reference the published paper (cited on the front of the attached document) and state, "Survey questions used with permission from Peer Assistance Service, Inc., Denver Colorado."

Does that work for you?

Please let me know if you have questions or need anything else.

Thanks,
Alexa

APPENDIX D**LETTER OF PERMISSION FROM HOSPITAL**

CSUF Institutional Review Board
Titan Hall – ASC 228
800 N. State College Blvd.
Fullerton, CA 92832

July 16, 2018

Dear CSUF IRB,

Based on my review of the proposed DNP project by Kate Bayhan, I give permission for her to conduct the project entitled "Evaluating Perceptions of Substance Use Disorder Among Emergency Nurses" within the Emergency Department of Placentia-Linda Hospital at 1301 N. Rose Dr., Placentia, CA 92870. As part of this study, I authorize the student to conduct an anonymous survey, analyze and disseminate survey data, and create an educational module based upon the collected data and literature review. Individuals' participation will be voluntary and at their own discretion.

We understand that our organization's responsibilities include: access to PLH EAP, if needed, and assistance with creating and disseminating education module in conjunction with the Department of Education. We reserve the right to withdraw from the project at any time if our circumstances change.

We understand that the research will include a brief anonymous paper-and-pencil survey and follow-up educational inservices.

This authorization covers the time period of July, 2018 to May, 2019.

I confirm that I am authorized to approve research in this setting.

I understand that the data collected will remain entirely confidential and may not be provided to anyone outside of the research team without permission from the California State University, Fullerton IRB.

Sincerely,

Nancy E Lee, MSHCM, BSN, NEA-BC
Chief Nursing Officer
O – 714-961-5940
M- 619-550-6506

1301 N. Rose Drive
Placentia, CA 92870

APPENDIX E

EMERGENCY SERVICE INDEX ALGORITHM

ESI Triage Algorithm, v4

Notes:

- A. **Immediate life-saving intervention required:** airway, emergency medications, or other hemodynamic interventions (IV, supplemental O₂, monitor, ECG or labs DC NOT count); and/or any of the following clinical conditions: intubated, apneic, pulseless, severe respiratory distress, SPO₂<90, acute mental status changes, or unresponsive.

Unresponsiveness is defined as a patient that is either:

- (1) nonverbal and not following commands (acutely); or
- (2) requires noxious stimulus (PU on AVPU) scale.

- B. **High risk situation** is a patient you would put in your last open bed.

Severe pain/distress is determined by clinical observation and/or patient rating of greater than or equal to 7 on 0-10 pain scale.

- C. **Resources:** Count the number of *different types* of resources, not the individual tests or x-rays (examples: CBC, electrolytes and coags equals one resource; CBC plus chest x-ray equals two resources).

<i>Resources</i>	<i>Not Resources</i>
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> •Labs (blood, urine) •ECG, X-rays •CT-MRI-ultrasound-angiography 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> •History & physical (including pelvic) •Point-of-care testing
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> •IV fluids (hydration) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> •Saline or heparin
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> •IV or IM or nebulized medications 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> •PO medications •Tetanus immunization •Prescription refills
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> •Specialty consultation 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> •Phone call to PCP
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> •Simple procedure =1 (bc repair, foley cath) •Complex procedure =2 (conscious sedation) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> •Simple wound care (dressings, recheck) •Crutches, splints, slings

- D. **Danger Zone Vital Signs**

Consider uptriage to ESI 2 if any vital sign criterion is exceeded.

Pediatric Fever Considerations

1 to 28 days of age: assign at least ESI 2 if temp >38.0 C (100.4F)

1-3 months of age: consider assigning ESI 2 if temp >38.0 C (100.4F)

3 months to 3 yrs of age: consider assigning ESI 3 if: temp >39.0 C (102.2 F), or incomplete immunizations, or no obvious source of fever

APPENDIX F

CALIFORNIA STATE UNIVERSITY FULLERTON RESEARCH STUDY COVER LETTER CONSENT

Study Title: Evaluating Perceptions of Substance Use Disorder Among Emergency Nurses

Protocol Number: *HSR-17-18-545*

Researchers: Kate Bayhan (graduate student), Dr. Roxanne O'Brien (faculty Chair), School of Nursing

You are being asked to take part in a research study carried out by Kate Bayhan. This cover letter consent form explains the research study and your part in it if you decide to join the study. Please read the form carefully, taking as much time as you need. Ask the researcher to explain anything you don't understand. You can decide not to join the study. If you join the study, you can change your mind later and leave the study at any time. There will be no penalty or loss of services or benefits if you decide to not take part in the study.

What is this study about?

This research study is being conducted to evaluate the underlying perceptions and knowledge about substance abuse and dependence among Emergency Nurses. The results of this survey will be used in to create an educational module to address misconceptions about substance use disorder. Taking part in the study will take about 15 minutes. You cannot take part in this study if you are under 18, you are not a registered nurse, you do not work primarily in the Emergency Department, or you are a nurse manager.

What will I be asked to do if I am in this study?

If you take part in the study, you will be asked to complete a five-item survey to assess your baseline perceptions and knowledge about substance use disorder among registered nurses. The survey will take approximately 15 minutes to complete.

Are there any benefits to me if I am in this study?

There is no direct benefit to you from being in this study. If you take part in this study, you may help others in the future and contribute to the baseline data needed to develop an educational module.

Are there any risks to me if I am in this study?

The potential risks from taking part in this study are distress or discomfort in response to the sensitive topic of the substance abuse/dependence. Precautions, such as content expert review and clearance through management and the Department of Human Resources, have been taken to minimize these risks. The final page contains referrals, counseling, and other services provided at no cost through Placentia-Linda Hospital.

Will my information be kept anonymous or confidential?

The data for this study are being collected anonymously. Neither the researcher(s) nor anyone else will be able to link data to you. Any surveys/responses will be stored in a locked office. The results of this study may be published or presented at professional meetings. The identities of all research participants will remain anonymous. The data for this study will be kept for 3 years after the completion of the study.

Are there any costs or payments for being in this study?

There will be no costs to you for taking part in this study.
You will not receive money or any other form of compensation for taking part in this study.

Who can I talk to if I have questions?

If you have questions about this study or the information in this form, please contact the researcher Kate Bayhan: skatebay@csu.fullerton.edu, cell phone: **714-931-1600**. If you have questions about your rights as a research participant, or would like to report a concern or complaint about this study, please contact the Institutional Review Board at (657) 278-7719, or e-mail irb@fullerton.edu

What are my rights as a research study volunteer?

Your participation in this research study is completely voluntary. You may choose not to be a part of this study. There will be no penalty to you if you choose not to take part. You may choose not to answer specific questions or to stop participating at any time. Your anonymity is further protected by not asking you to sign and return a consent form. Your completion of the survey will serve as your consent. Please keep this cover letter for future reference.

HSR-17-18-545

APPENDIX G

EMPLOYEE ASSISTANCE PROGRAM RESOURCES

Contact Us... Anytime, Anywhere

No-cost, confidential solutions to life's challenges.

Confidential Emotional Support

Our highly trained clinicians will listen to your concerns and help you or your family members with any issues, including:

- Anxiety, depression, stress
- Grief, loss and life adjustments
- Relationship/marital conflicts

Work-Life Solutions

Our specialists provide qualified referrals and resources for just about anything on your to-do list, such as:

- Finding child and elder care
- Hiring movers or home repair contractors
- Planning events, locating pet care

Legal Guidance

Talk to our attorneys for practical assistance with your most pressing legal issues, including:

- Divorce, adoption, family law, wills, trusts and more
- Need representation? Get a free 30-minute consultation and a 25% reduction in fees.

Financial Resources

Our financial experts can assist with a wide range of issues. Talk to us about:

- Retirement planning, taxes
- Relocation, mortgages, insurance
- Budgeting, debt, bankruptcy and more

Online Support

GuidanceResources® Online is your 24/7 link to vital information, tools and support. Log on for:

- Articles, podcasts, videos, slideshows
- On-demand trainings
- "Ask the Expert" personal responses to your questions

Tobacco Cessation

HealthyGuidance® gives you the tools to quit smoking for good, including:

- 1-on-1 counseling with a certified coach
- A personalized quit plan
- Online support and information

Your ComPsych® GuidanceResources® program offers someone to talk to and resources to consult whenever and wherever you need them.

Call: 844.416.1158

TDD: 800.897.0353

Your toll-free number gives you direct, 24/7 access to a GuidanceConsultant™, who will answer your questions and, if needed, refer you to a counselor or other resources.

Employees: mytenet.com

Family Members:
guidanceresources.com

App: GuidanceResources® Now
Web ID: Tenet

Log on today to connect directly with a GuidanceConsultant about your issue or to consult articles, podcasts, videos and other helpful tools.

24/7 Support, Resources & Information

Contact Your GuidanceResources® Program

Call: 844.416.1158 TDD: 800.897.0353

Employees: mytenet.com

Family Members: guidanceresources.com

App: GuidanceResources® Now

Web ID: Tenet

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APPENDIX H**APPROVAL NOTICE FROM INSTITUTIONAL REVIEW BOARD AT
CALIFORNIA STATE UNIVERSITY, FULLERTON****CALIFORNIA STATE UNIVERSITY, FULLERTON***Office of Research and Sponsored Projects*

P.O. Box 6850 or 1121 N. State College Blvd., 2nd Fl., Fullerton, CA 92831 / T 657-278-7719 / F 657-278-7238

APPROVAL NOTICE*From the Institutional Review Board
California State University, Fullerton***July 20, 2018****From: Dr. Matt Englar-Carlson, Chair
CSUF Institutional Review Board****To: PI: S. Kate Bayhan**

Application No. HSR-17-18-545

Study Title: Evaluating Perceptions of Substance Use Disorder Among Emergency Nurses

Re: Initial Exempt Review

The forms you submitted to this office regarding the use of human participants in the above-referenced proposal have been reviewed by the Regulatory Compliance Coordinator and the Chair of the California State University, Fullerton, Institutional Review Board. Your proposal is determined to be Category 2. Research involving the use of educational tests (cognitive, diagnostic, aptitude, achievement), survey procedures, interview procedures or observation of public behavior, unless: (i) information obtained is recorded in such a manner that human subjects can be identified, directly or through identifiers linked to the subjects; and (ii) any disclosure of the human subjects' responses outside the research could reasonably place the subjects at risk of criminal or civil liability or be damaging to the subjects' financial standing, employability, or reputation.

The CSUF IRB has not evaluated your proposal for scientific merit, except to weigh the risk to the human participants and the aspects of the proposal related to potential risk and benefit. This approval notice does not replace any departmental or additional approvals which may be required.

It is of utmost importance that you strictly adhere to the guidelines for human participants and that you follow the plan/methodology/procedures described in your research proposal. Since your proposed was determined to be

exempt, there is no further review or annual renewal required by the CSUF IRB. **However, any change in protocol or consent form procedure requires re-submission to the CSUF IRB for approval prior to implementation.** Additionally, the principal investigator must promptly report, in writing, any unanticipated or adverse events causing risks to research participants or others.

Please be advised that if you are seeking external funding for this proposal, the above-reference title should match exactly with the title submitted to the funding sponsor. Any changes in project title should be submitted to the CSUF IRB prior to implementation.

By copy of this notice, the chair of your department (and/or co-investigator) is reminded that their responsibility for being informed concerning research projects involving human participants in the department, and should review all protocols of such investigations as often as needed to ensure that the project is being conducted in compliance with our institutional policies and with DHHS regulations.

The institution has an Assurance on file with the Office of Human Research Protections. The Assurance Number is FWA00015384.

Cc: IRB Office
Roxanne O'Brien

APPENDIX I
EDUCATIONAL INSERVICE

Substance Use Disorder Among
Emergency Nurses

February 1, 2018

Five-Item Survey Results:

- 27 completed surveys (66% response rate)
- Demographics:
 - 74% of respondents were female
 - Even distribution between shifts – AM, Cross, NOC
 - 50% have 0 – 5 years of experience
- Significant Responses:
 - 19 nurses said they can identify an impaired coworker
 - 8 nurses (30%) said they *cannot* identify an impaired coworker
- 50% of respondents believed SUD affects >15% of RNs
- While 23 nurses identified “Entry into treatment program,” responses were varied

What Do You Think Happens If You Report?

Substance Use Disorder

- **Definition:** Chronic and progressive disease that includes a spectrum of alcohol and/or drug use, from abuse to dependence

(National Council of State Boards of Nursing [NCSBN], 2011)

- More than 50% of individuals with SUD also struggle with mental illness
- Significant social stigma surrounding mental illness and SUD
- National Institute of Drug Abuse estimates 40 to 60% of people with SUD are genetically predisposed

National Statistics

- \$740 **billion** in costs related to healthcare, treatment, lost productivity, and crime related to substance abuse (National Institute of Health [NIH], 2014)
- Since 1999, **five-fold** increase in overdose-related **deaths** (Centers for Disease Control and Prevention [CDC], 2017)
- Estimated **115** fatal overdoses per day (CDC, 2017)

Nursing Statistics

- Exact numbers are hard to obtain
- Estimated **6 - 20%** of nurses have substance abuse/dependence issues (Bozimowski et al., 2014; ENA, 2016; NCSBN, 2011)
- If mirroring general population prevalence (10%), **300,000** RNs have SUD (NCSBN, 2011)
- **< 1%** (n=17,085) of nurses are enrolled in ATD or disciplinary programs each year (Monroe et al., 2013)

Impact to Nurses

(Weenink et al., 2017)

- Risk to patient safety
- Risk to individual's health
- Risk to healthcare team

Risk Factors

(Cares et al., 2015; Darbro & Malliarkis, 2013; Lala et al., 2016; Pilgrim et al., 2017; Ross et al., 2017; Strobbe & Crowley, 2017)

- Work overload and stress
- Poor coping
- Family history of SUD or mental illness
- Chronic pain
- Understanding of pharmacology
- Access to medications

Barriers to Reporting

- Lack of knowledge of policies and consequences (Ross et al., 2017; Worley, 2017)
- Embarrassment and hopelessness (Cares et al., 2015)
- Lack of employer support (Cares et al., 2015)
- Low confidence in capacity to identify impaired colleagues (Cares et al., 2015; Kunky, 2015)
- Misconceptions about prevalence of SUD (Cares et al., 2015; Darbro & Malliarakis, 2013)

Potential Risks to Employer

Civil Liability

- Employers are liable for patient harm while under the care of impaired employees

Regulatory Liability

- Failure to prevent or report signs of drug diversion or impaired coworkers may prompt inspections from:
 - Joint Commission
 - Centers for Medicare and Medicaid Services (CMS)
 - Drug Enforcement Administration (DEA) nces

Early Detection and Intervention

- Coworkers are first-line in early detection of RN impairment (Cares et al., 2015)
- Mandatory continuing education on SUD (Zickafoose, 2018)
- Hospital policies that support Alternative to Discipline (ATD) programs (Wright et al., 2014)

Proactive Monitoring

- **Documentation**
 - Maintain rigid inventory of controlled substances
 - Mandatory co-signature for enhanced accountability
 - Timely accounting for discrepancies
- **Routine Monitoring**
 - Evaluate high-usage drugs
 - Routine monitoring of controlled substances
- **Non-Punitive Reporting**
 - Establish a culture of safety
 - Use collaborative approach to ensure prevention

What To Do If You Suspect Diversion

- Immediately notify manager

- OR -

- Contact Ethics Action Line:
Toll Free: 800-38-4427
Fax: 469-893-7341
Email: ethics@tenethealth.com

Placentia-Linda Hospital's Policy

Hospital policy is available on intranet:

<https://plh.ellucid.com/documents/view/5677>

Recent update 12-1-2018

Employees are responsible for strict adherence to hospital policy

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Post Test

1. What is substance use disorder?
2. How many RNs does the NCSBN estimate currently have SUD?
3. What are some risk factors? Select all that apply
4. What happens if you report a coworker you suspect of impairment?
5. What is PLH's policy on SUD among nurses?

APPENDIX J**HOSPITAL-SPECIFIC POLICY FOR CONTROLLED SUBSTANCE
DIVERSION PREVENTION AND DETECTION**

Administrative

Subject:

**Controlled Substance
Diversion Prevention and
Detection**

Page 1 of 9

Effective Date: 12/1/2018

Reviewed/Revised: 11/2018

Previous Versions Dated:

Governing Board Approval

Date: 12/11/2017

Medical Staff Approval Date:

11/28/2017

I. SCOPE:

This policy applies to (1) Tenet Healthcare Corporation and its wholly-owned subsidiaries and affiliates (each, an “Affiliate”); (2) any other entity or organization in which Tenet Healthcare Corporation or an Affiliate owns a direct or indirect equity interest greater than 50%, and (3) any hospital or entity in which an Affiliate either manages or controls the day-to-day operations of the entity (each, a “Tenet Entity”) (collectively, “Tenet”).

II. PURPOSE:

The purpose of this policy is to establish controls related to controlled substance security and monitoring to prevent and detect diversion.

III. DEFINITIONS:

A. “**Automated medication supply system**” means a mechanical system that performs operations or activities relative to the secure storage and distribution of medications for administration and which collects, controls and maintains all transaction information.

B. “**Authorized Personnel**” means a person approved or assigned to perform a specific type of duty or duties.

C. “**Controlled substance**” means drugs and or other substances that are considered Schedule II through Schedule V controlled substances under the Controlled Substances Act. An updated and complete list of controlled substance schedules is published annually in Title 21 Code of Federal Regulations (C.F.R.) §§ 1308.11 through 1308.15.

D. “**Discrepancies**” means the inventory count of a controlled substance is incorrect.

E. “**Directly supervised**” means under supervision of a licensed pharmacist who is

on the premises at all times while tasks are being performed; who is fully aware of all delegated tasks being performed; and who is readily available to provide assistance and direction throughout the time the delegated tasks are being performed.

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F. “**Diversion**” means the illegal distribution or abuse of prescription drugs or their use for purposes not intended by the prescriber. This may include deflection of prescription drugs from medical sources into the illegal market.

G. “**Non-retrievable**” means the process utilized to permanently alter the substance’s physical or chemical condition or state through irreversible means and thereby render the substance unavailable and unusable for all practical purposes. A substance is considered “non-retrievable” when it cannot be transformed to a physical or chemical condition or state as a controlled substance or controlled substance analogue.

H. Regarding “**Significant loss**,” there is no single objective standard that can be established and applied to all DEA registrants to determine whether a loss is significant. Any unexplained loss or discrepancy should be reviewed within the context of a registrant’s business activity and environment. When in doubt, registrants should consult Tenet legal for determination.

IV. POLICY:

In order to detect intentional or unintentional breach of procedure in the management of controlled substances, each Tenet Entity procuring controlled substances shall establish processes for controlled substance procurement, storage and access, wastage, and monitoring to prevent and detect diversion.

V. PROCEDURE:

A. Controlled Substance Procurement and Inventory

1. Each Tenet Entity procuring controlled substances shall have and maintain an inventory system that assures accuracy of all controlled substances.

The inventory system may be either manual or computerized as long as the disposition of all controlled substances (*e.g.*, all controlled substances received, dispensed to nursing units, expired, wasted or returned to reverse distributors) is accurately tracked. Only pharmacists and directly supervised pharmacy technicians are permitted to have access to the pharmacy controlled substance secured storage location.

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2. Different individuals shall perform the ordering and receiving of controlled substances functions unless mitigating circumstances prevent this from occurring. In such instances, Tenet Entities shall implement compensating controls (*e.g.*, additional independent reviews/audits).
3. All drug orders for procured medications (*e.g.*, wholesaler, manufacturer, borrowed) shall be delivered directly to the Pharmacy Department. Only Authorized Personnel shall be allowed to “receive” such orders, at which time the number of delivery totes or boxes shall be counted for comparison to the delivery manifest, if applicable. If a tote or box is missing, it shall be noted on the manifest before signing acceptance of the delivery and the supplier immediately contacted. If a discrepancy, shortage or breakage is found within a tote or box upon opening, the Authorized Personnel shall immediately contact the supplier and document the incident on the packing slip or invoice.
4. The Director of Pharmacy shall randomly select three (3) Schedule II and three (3) Schedule III-V controlled substance deliveries per month and confirm the presence of proper documentation and that the quantities ordered match the quantities received into inventory.
5. A physical inventory (manual count) of all controlled substances in pharmacy or Automated Medication Supply System single-dose dispensers (*e.g.*, OmniDispenser) shall be performed at a minimum of once monthly, and once weekly anywhere controlled substances are stored outside of pharmacy, or for cause. Weekly controlled substance inventories shall be completed by the respective department’s Manager/Supervisor or designee. The inventory shall be completed for all controlled substances, including those that were not accessed during that time frame, and the inventory documented.
6. When Authorized Personnel transporting controlled substance inventory to any location outside of pharmacy, the controlled substances shall be kept secure and in a lock box, if available.

B. Controlled Substance Storage and Access

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1. Automated Medication Supply System Controls

a. Settings of all automated medication supply systems shall have a timed password-reset at least every 90 days and automatic user logout no greater than 90 seconds. Biometric identification (fingerprint) is the preferred method for access. If biometric identification is deployed, users able to login with a password shall be limited and by exception only (*e.g.*, fingerprints not readable by biometric scanner). Anesthesia workstations in procedural rooms may have extended automatic user logouts, and users shall logout of the system upon conclusion of the case or physically leaving the cabinet.

b. Only Tenet Entity pharmacy or IT Authorized Personnel shall have access to the automated medication supply system server. Only the Director of Pharmacy or Tenet Entity pharmacy Authorized Personnel may have access to create users or reset passwords. Only the Director of Pharmacy, Nurse Manager/Supervisor or pharmacy Authorized Personnel shall have the ability to create temporary users at the cabinet. Temporary usernames shall remain active for no more than 24 hours.

c. If users with automated medication supply system access have changes in employment/contract status or Tenet Entity privileges which would preclude them from having access to medications, the Director of Pharmacy or Tenet Entity pharmacy Authorized Personnel shall be promptly notified so they may deactivate the user's access.

d. Each Tenet Entity shall maintain a process for review of discrepancies and overrides as required by Administrative Policy AD 1.21 Pharmacy Control Processes Section V.A.1.c.

Discrepancy and Override Reports.

2. Controlled Substances Stored Outside of Automated Medication Supply Systems

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- a. Controlled substances in patient care areas, pharmacy and/or designated storage areas without automated medication supply systems are to be locked in a safe or steel cabinet of substantial construction that is stored in a locked area.
- b. Controlled substances distributed to a patient care area without an automated medication supply system shall be recorded on a nursing Controlled Substance Administration Record (CSAR) by the pharmacy Authorized Personnel delivering the controlled substance and a licensed individual working in the area.
- c. In areas without an automated medication supply system, two licensed individuals working in the area shall reconcile controlled medications on the CSAR at the beginning and/or end of each shift.
- d. Controlled substances shall not be stored in crash/emergency carts.

3. Patient-Owned Controlled Substances

- a. Each Tenet Entity shall adopt a policy in the form of Clinical Operations model policy CO-3.004 Medications Brought to the Hospital by the Patient, requiring patient-owned controlled substances be sent home with family members/patient representative when possible. Patient-owned controlled substances not sent home shall be logged and kept in a locked location or automated medication supply system.
- b. If patient-owned controlled substances cannot be returned to the patient, they shall be discarded within 30 days post-discharge. Destruction shall be performed and documented by two (2) licensed individuals, and shall render the substance nonretrievable.

C. Controlled Substance Wastage

Administrative

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Controlled Substance

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1. Any controlled substance packaged in an amount larger than the dose being administered (*i.e.*, excess controlled substance not administered) shall be wasted in a timely manner and prior to the end of each shift.
2. Wastage documentation will be performed by two (2) licensed individuals, one of whom is an employee of the Tenet Entity.
3. Signatures of each individual involved with the wastage of a controlled substance medication shall be performed electronically or directly onto the manual documentation form.
4. Wastage destruction shall render the substance non-retrievable.

D. Controlled Substance Monitoring and Response

1. Drug Diversion Prevention Committee and Tenet Entity

a. Each Tenet Entity shall establish a multidisciplinary Drug Diversion Prevention Committee consisting of, at a minimum, an administrator, the Chief Nursing Officer, Director of Pharmacy and members of the compliance, pharmacy and nursing departments. The Drug Diversion Prevention Committee is tasked with preventing, monitoring and responding to incidents of drug diversion.

b. The Drug Diversion Prevention Committee and/or Authorized Personnel assigned by the Tenet Entity's Chief Executive Officer shall review controlled substance trend and usage pattern reports at least quarterly.

c. The Drug Diversion Prevention Committee and/or Authorized Personnel assigned by the Tenet Entity's Chief Executive Officer shall promptly investigate all thefts, significant losses or inventory discrepancies and other potential diversion of controlled substances and will report them to the Tenet Entity's Chief Executive Officer, Compliance Officer, Human Resources, Tenet Administrative

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legal counsel, and Tenet Corporate Security as required by the following Tenet policies:

- Administrative policy AD 1.21 Pharmacy Control Processes
- Corporate Security policy CS 2.42 Reporting of Theft of

Assets and Property

- Regulatory Compliance policy COMP-RCC 4.21 Internal Reporting of Potential Compliance Matters
- Human Resource policy HR.EHP.18 Drug and Alcohol Free Workplace and Drug and/or Alcohol Testing
- Human Resource policy HR.ERW.09 Employee Conduct and Work Rules

In addition, the Tenet Entity and the Drug Diversion Prevention Committee shall report all diversions to the Drug Enforcement Administration (DEA), local law enforcement and State regulatory agencies (*e.g.*, board of nursing, board of pharmacy, board of medicine, etc.) immediately.

(1) Theft – Discovery of any theft regardless of amount shall be reported immediately. Where circumstances of the theft are immediately known, a DEA Form 106, Report of Theft or Loss of Controlled Substances, shall be used to detail the circumstances of that theft. When details concerning the specific circumstances surrounding the theft are unknown at the time of discovery, initial notice should be provided by faxing a short statement to local DEA advising of the theft.

(2) Significant Loss – Where circumstances of significant loss are known, a DEA Form 106, Report of Theft or Loss of Administrative

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Controlled Substances, shall be used to detail the circumstances of that significant loss.

2. Controlled Substance Surveillance Software

- a. The Tenet Entity shall deploy controlled substance surveillance software, which produces user-friendly reports of automated medication supply system data indicating potential diversion.
- b. The Pharmacy Department shall conduct daily reviews of automated medication supply system reports, which may include but is not limited to:

(1) Instances where more than a certain number of doses were

dispensed at one time for one patient (“greater than” reports)

(2) Destock/expiration verifications

(3) Null transactions

(4) Controlled substance overrides and discrepancies

c. The Pharmacy Department shall conduct operating room post case reconciliation of controlled substances dispensed, used or wasted, and, if any discrepancy is not resolved within 72 hours, to report the discrepancy to the Director of Pharmacy.

d. At least one nursing leader per clinical area shall conduct monthly reviews of all controlled substance surveillance software anomalous usage and/or controlled substances dispensed reports for the automated medication supply systems in that clinical area. The Chief Nursing Officer shall conduct monthly compliance checks on their nursing leader direct reports to ensure the reports are being reviewed.

E. Training

The Drug Diversion Prevention Committee shall conduct and/or facilitate training during orientation and annual training for all staff with access to controlled Administrative

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substances, including training on the signs and symptoms of substance abuse and addiction, drug diversion monitoring and prevention, the duty to report and the filing of safety reports.

F. Responsible Person

Each Tenet Entity Chief Executive Officer, Director of Pharmacy and/or Pharmacist In Charge is responsible for ensuring that all individuals adhere to the requirements of this policy, that these procedures are implemented and followed at Facility and that instances of non-compliance with this policy are reported to the Compliance Officer.

G. Enforcement

All employees whose responsibilities are affected by this policy are expected to be familiar with the basic procedures and responsibilities created by this policy. Failure to comply with this policy will be subject to appropriate performance management pursuant to all applicable policies and procedures, up to and including termination. Such performance management may also include

modification of compensation, including any merit or discretionary compensation awards, as allowed by applicable law.

VI. REFERENCES

Administrative policy AD 1.21 Pharmacy Control Processes

Clinical Operations policy CO-3.004 Medications Brought to the Hospital by the Patient

Corporate Security policy CS 2.42 Reporting of Theft of Assets and Property

Human Resource policy HR.EHP.18 Drug and Alcohol Free Workplace and Drug and/or Alcohol Testing

Regulatory Compliance policy COMP-RCC 4.21 Internal Reporting of Potential Compliance

Matters